

COVID-19 preparedness and response: shortcomings and opportunities.

- An initial analysis for EU policymakers -

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Executive summary

The COVID-19 pandemic exposed significant shortcomings in the preparedness and response mechanisms of EU Member States, revealing critical vulnerabilities in national healthcare systems including underfunded preparedness, supply chain disruptions, decentralized decision-making, and inadequate public communication. These issues led to overwhelmed healthcare systems, delayed responses, and public mistrust, exacerbating the health and economic impacts of the crisis.

This report, *"COVID-19 Preparedness and Response: Shortcomings and Opportunities – An Initial Analysis for EU Policymakers"*, provides a comprehensive evaluation of the pandemic responses in Denmark, France, Latvia, Italy, and Spain (the target countries), highlighting their preparedness systems, response strategies, and lessons learned. It marks the outcome of the work conducted during the first year of the EU-funded PAIR project, which aims to improve pandemic preparedness and response through technology and modelling. Within PAIR, two key components are being developed, which are the PANPOC diagnostic system for rapid virus detection and the PANRISK platform for predicting virus spread. By addressing the identified shortcomings and leveraging technologies like PANPOC and PANRISK, EU policymakers can enhance preparedness, improve response capabilities, and build more resilient health systems.

Policy recommendations

- **Enhance data integration, harmonization, and utilization:** Invest in digital infrastructure to improve data collection, harmonization, and accessibility. Technologies like PANPOC and PANRISK can streamline data integration and provide actionable insights for decision-making.
- **Institutionalize comprehensive surveillance and prevention measures:** Establish permanent surveillance systems for early detection and response to infectious disease threats. PAIR technologies can support proactive surveillance and risk assessment.
- **Bolster international cooperation and coordination:** Strengthen international cooperation to share information, best practices, and resources. PAIR technologies can facilitate coordinated response efforts and evaluate the effectiveness of different strategies.
- **Support supply chain resilience:** Ensure continuity in the supply of critical goods during a pandemic. PAIR technologies can support proactive management of resources and forecast potential supply chain disruptions.
- **Promote equitable, inclusive, and accessible health services:** Address systemic inequities and ensure universal health coverage. PAIR technologies can support inclusive data collection and informed decision-making.

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List of Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
APAs	Advance Purchase Agreements
CE	European Conformity
COVARs	French Committee for Monitoring and Anticipating Health Risks
CRII	Coronavirus Response Investment Initiative
DG	Directorate-General
DGS	Direction Générale de la Santé
DMA	Danish Medicines Agency
ECDC	European Centre for Disease Control
EHU	European Health Union
ESI	Emergency Support Instrument
EU	European Union
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
HERA	Health Emergency Preparedness and Response Authority
HiAP	Health in All Policies
ICU	Intensive Care Unit

JPA	Joint Procurement Agreement
ML	Machine Learning
NOST	National Operative Staff
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PPE	Personal Protective Equipment
POC	Point of Care
RRF	European Union's Recovery and Resilience Facility
RNA	Ribonucleic Acid
SAM	Scientific Advice Mechanism
SDGs	UN Sustainable Goals
SI-DEP	Système d'Information de DEPistage
UCPM	European Civil Protection Mechanism
USD	United States Dollar
VAT	Value Added Tax
WHO	World Health Organisation
8th EAP	General Union Environment Action Programme to 2030

1 Introduction

1.1 Overview of the PAIR project

The [PAIR](#) project aims to address the pressing challenge of ensuring transparent, faster, and more informed decision-making in the context of pandemic preparedness and response. Leveraging the power of technology and modelling, **the project seeks to provide rapid, reliable, and cost-effective information to aid informed decision-making and support public trust.**

A key aspect of the project is the monitoring and detection of emerging pathogens in domestic animals, wildlife reservoirs, and the environment, to enable prompt containment measures and pandemic threat assessments. Testing and genomic sequencing of positive samples will be fundamental to the development of prediction models to support pandemic preparedness plans.

PAIR will develop rapid and reliable detection methods for respiratory RNA viruses and foster pandemic preparedness thanks to two ambitious and interactive technologies: **PANPOC** and **PANRISK**. Based on past pandemics, PAIR identified respiratory RNA target viruses to be detected: human and animal Influenza A (InfA, AIV and SIV), Influenza B and beta-CoV (SARS-CoV-2 variants and emerging beta-coronaviruses).

The PAIR project proposes **a solution that will contribute to the EU's comprehensive One Health genomic-informed surveillance and outbreak response model**, by ensuring the availability of state-of-the-art point-of-care systems and prognostic Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML)-based models in the EU. The prompt availability of appropriate diagnostic and risk assessment tools will enhance Europe's pandemic preparedness and response capabilities.

1.1.1 The PANPOC diagnostic system

PANPOC is a diagnostic point-of-care (POC) portable instrument for rapid detection of respiratory RNA viruses with pandemic potential in human, animal, and environmental samples. PANPOC integrates heater and optical detection systems. Its pioneering technology builds on a real-time fluorescence-based detection which can be used for both clinical diagnostics (human samples) and veterinary surveillance.

PANPOC simple design with a touchscreen, together with the high level of integration, isothermal amplification, and real-time analysis of multiple samples, will greatly enhance its applicability and portability.

It will be targeted at health authorities, veterinary and clinical end-users, and primary care providers, to provide them with a reliable, portable instrument for fast and highly-accurate RNA respiratory virus detection.

1.1.2 The PANRISK platform

PANRISK is a prognostic AI-based model combining a spillover model (to predict risk of animal pathogens spillover that can infect humans) and an epidemiologic model (to predict spatial-temporal outbreaks).

PANRISK is especially well positioned for surveillance of zoonotic diseases and will help predict the spread of the target viruses and contribute to public health by giving an alarm once an outbreak exceeds a given threshold. In detail:

- **PANRISK spillover model** keeps monitoring animal pathogenic viruses and genomic variation to predict human infection and the cross-border risk of spillover. Based on relevant data sources, it will trace epidemic trajectories (growth rate, reproduction numbers), ecological interactions (i.e. host spillover rates) and spatial-temporal patterns (diffusion rates, source-sink dynamics)
- **PANRISK epidemiologic model** consists of an automated and continuous outbreaks monitoring to give alarm when viruses exceed appropriate thresholds based on test data. It takes input from different diseases with similar transmission mode, across animal and human populations, seasons, and countries by using public sequence databases

1.2 Scope and purpose of this document

This report concludes the first year of activities related to Task 10.5 - *Integration and deployment in health policies and healthcare systems*.

This document presents a comprehensive overview of COVID-19 responses in the project's Target Countries: Denmark, France, Latvia, Italy, and Spain. The analysis of key needs, expectations, shortcomings, and opportunities detailed in this report adopts a holistic approach, including a review of existing literature, data analysis, and structured interviews with senior policy and decision-makers in the aforementioned countries.

The goal is to support senior EU policymakers in managing pandemics and mitigating their impact on public health and the economy, ensuring that PAIR's tools, PANPOC and PANRISK, serve as valuable resources for pandemic preparedness and response.

This report takes a country-based approach, integrating desk research to offer an overview of each target country's COVID-19 pandemic preparedness and response with qualitative interviews for a deeper analysis. It explores the key measures and strategies adopted, their outcomes and impacts, the challenges encountered, and the good practices and lessons learned. The findings are summarized in tables to enable cross-country comparisons, followed by an analysis of the identified shortcomings and lessons learned.

Finally, Europe's response to the pandemic is assessed, focusing on the EU's public health strategies, including the European Health Union and vaccine procurement efforts, and its

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financial commitment to health. It highlights the "One Health" approach linking human, animal, and environmental health and discusses the EU's role in developing the WHO pandemic treaty to enhance global pandemic preparedness and response. Lastly, recommendations for EU policymakers are proposed as well as the possible benefits from the integration of PAIR technologies.

1.3 Methodology

The qualitative research strategy employed in this study involved a series of in-depth, semi-structured interviews with key informants, carefully selected **based on their central roles in pandemic management and policy design**. This methodological approach was designed to complement prior desk research and quantitative data by providing insights that are not readily available through other sources. The semi-structured interview format allowed for a flexible, yet focused exploration of themes directly linked to pandemic preparedness and response, offering rich, context-specific perspectives.

Key informants were identified and selected based on the relevance of their roles and responsibilities in relation to the research objectives, ensuring their insights would contribute meaningfully to the analysis. This targeted approach, which prioritizes obtaining high-quality, nuanced insights from a relatively small yet highly specialized panel of interviewees, aligns with best practices in qualitative research. By focusing on depth rather than breadth, it captures rich, context-specific information and diverse perspectives that are essential for understanding complex phenomena, such as country based pandemic preparedness and response, making it particularly effective for exploratory and interpretative studies. Examples of respondents include senior policymakers and public health officials.

The interview process followed a structured, step-by-step approach:

- Project partners were consulted to recommend potential respondents with significant experience and influence in pandemic response.
- Potential respondents were informed about the study's scope and objectives, and interviews were scheduled. Each semi-structured interview lasted approximately one hour. Following established qualitative research protocols, the interviews were conducted remotely and recorded with the explicit consent of respondents.
- Transcripts were prepared and used only after receiving explicit approval from the respondents.
- Data analysis was carried out and integrated in the report.

At this early stage of the project, priority was given to the quality of information rather than the quantity of interviews. A total of nine interviews were conducted across four countries, distributed as follows: one each in Latvia, Italy, and Denmark, and six in France. This approach facilitated a focused and in-depth exploration of key issues, laying a solid foundation for the project's upcoming phases".

2 Covid-19 preparedness and response: country-by-country analysis

The pandemic affected all the EU Member States, but its impact varies considerably from country to country as does their ability to absorb and respond to the economic and health crisis. The effectiveness of country responses to the COVID-19 pandemic relies on national preparedness systems that are part of the global public health emergency framework, governed and coordinated by the [WHO's 2005 International Health Regulations](#).

In this chapter we examine:

1. The responses of the five target countries involved in PAIR (Denmark, France, Latvia, Italy, and Spain);
2. The political-administrative organization of pandemic preparedness and the respective response systems;
3. Macro shortcomings and challenges identified in pandemic response, as well as the lessons learned from them, the good practices to be enhanced and replicated for future health crisis.

2.1 Denmark

National health system in a nutshell

Denmark's national health system is a universal, tax-financed system that provides comprehensive benefits to all residents. It consists of three administrative levels: state, region, and municipal. The state holds regulatory, supervisory, and fiscal functions, while the five regions are responsible for hospitals and primary care services. Municipalities handle rehabilitation, long-term care, and public health. Most health spending is public, with 85% funded by government through general taxation (higher than the EU average of 81%).

2.1.1 Key measures and strategies

Lockdown measures

Denmark was one of the first countries to impose restrictions in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. On March 11, 2020, the Danish government announced a **nationwide lockdown** to "flatten the curve" and protect hospital capacity. This **suppression strategy** was supported by the precautionary principle.

It should be noted that the lockdown measures were not particularly strict compared to other European countries: borders were closed, and assemblies of more than ten individuals were banned, but the government never required all businesses to close, did not issue mandatory stay-at-home orders, never restricted internal travel, and maintained public transit.

Denmark was also one of the first countries to exit the lockdown on April 6, 2020, and the loosening of social distancing measures began mid-April. By June, the cap on assemblies was lifted from ten to fifty, and travel restrictions were rolled back, with visitors and Danes from selected countries exempted from self-isolation requirements.

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Public health strategies

The country's public healthcare system, characterized by universal health coverage, ensured that **all citizens had free and equal access to healthcare services**. The healthcare system is largely **decentralized**, which **facilitated effective collaboration across different levels of government, essential for managing the complexities of the COVID-19 pandemic**.

Throughout the pandemic, a significant concern was the risk of overburdening hospitals. To address this, wards for COVID-19 patients were established at existing hospitals, and clinical personnel were reassigned and trained to ensure sufficient resources. Non-acute appointments were postponed, and regions planned for extraordinary high-intensive care capacity and increased numbers of beds and isolation units at medical wards.

Extensive testing was a key element of Denmark's management of the pandemic. The country achieved **one of the highest testing capacities in Europe**, which corresponded to the entire population being tested in just eight days.

Denmark's vaccination rollout was similarly rapid and effective. Once vaccines were approved, the Danish Health Authority planned the vaccination program which began in December 2020, and the country quickly achieved high vaccination rates, with 82% of the population fully vaccinated by the summer of 2022. The vaccination program was voluntary and prioritized vulnerable groups and the elderly. **Denmark's robust digital infrastructure facilitated a smooth rollout and played a pivotal role in its effective response** to the COVID-19 pandemic. The country's advanced digital systems facilitated the collection and analysis of reliable data on the virus, enabling swift and informed decision-making. Digital solutions, such as the corona passport (introduced in March 2021 and integrated into *Sundhed.dk*) and contact tracing apps, were integral to controlling the spread of the virus while providing citizens with easy access to their health information, COVID-19 test results, and vaccination records.

Economic support

Denmark's response to the economic challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic was characterized by **prompt decision-making and widespread social support**. The country implemented a **temporary wage compensation program** to protect jobs and support businesses adversely affected by the crisis.

The government also agreed to cover 25% to 100% of the fixed costs for businesses adversely affected by the crisis, representing a significant commitment to protect established enterprises. This was flanked by the deferral of Value Added Tax (VAT) payments, labour market contributions, and withheld income tax payments, providing additional liquidity. The government also used a suite of instruments to deliver emergency recapitalization, loan guarantees, export credits, and a sector-specific bailout of the travel industry.

2.1.2 Outcomes and impact

Denmark's strategic and comprehensive approach to managing the COVID-19 pandemic yielded significant positive outcomes and impacts across various dimensions. The country's ability to leverage its digital infrastructure, maintain high public trust, and implement robust testing and vaccination programs contributed to its success in mitigating the health and economic impacts of the pandemic.

Health impact

One of the most notable outcomes was Denmark's relatively **low excess mortality rate** throughout the pandemic. The country consistently ranked among the European nations with the lowest excess mortality. This achievement can be attributed to the comprehensive testing strategy, the rapid and effective vaccination rollout, and the swift implementation of restrictions and the subsequent lifting of these measures as the situation improved. This balanced approach allowed Denmark to maintain a strong economy and a well-functioning society while minimizing the health impact of the virus.

Economic impact

The economic outcomes of Denmark's response were also favourable. The country demonstrated **one of the faster economic recoveries among OECD nations**. Denmark's prompt decision-making and extensive use of digital tools to support healthcare, comprehensive testing, and rapid vaccination facilitated a quicker economic rebound. **The Danish experience highlighted the value of prompt decision-making, public trust, and investments in digitalization and health systems**. The economic support measures, including the temporary wage compensation program and various loan guarantees, helped protect jobs and support businesses, contributing to the country's economic resilience.

Social impact

The social impact of Denmark's COVID-19 response was largely positive, characterized by **high public trust** and **widespread compliance** with public health measures. The Danish government's transparent, timely, and clear communication with citizens built and maintained public trust, which was reflected in the high level of support for public guidelines and measures. Combined with the use of digital tools, it facilitated compliance with the comprehensive testing strategy and vaccination program, which were instrumental in building immunity in the Danish population.

2.1.3 Shortcomings and challenges

Despite the numerous successes in Denmark's management of the COVID-19 pandemic, several shortcomings and challenges emerged that warrant careful examination. These issues highlight areas where improvements could be made and provide valuable lessons for future pandemic preparedness and response efforts.

Preparedness and initial response

One significant challenge was the **initial underestimation of the virus's impact** and the delayed implementation of certain measures. In January 2020, the Danish Health Authority (DHA) assessed the probability of COVID-19 entering Denmark as very low, recommending neither screenings of individuals traveling from nor travel restrictions to known high-risk areas. As the likelihood of the virus spreading grew, **the country adopted a containment strategy, which later shifted to a suppression strategy as infection rates rose**. This transition, while necessary, **revealed a lag in the initial response** that could have been addressed more promptly.

The decision-making process also faced challenges, particularly regarding the alignment between political decisions and expert advice. The political choice of a suppression strategy, although highly effective in reducing infection rates and hospitalizations, contrasted with the DHA's initial recommendation for a mitigation strategy. This discrepancy between political actions and expert recommendations highlighted the complexities of balancing public health needs with economic and social considerations.

Public communication and trust

Although Denmark maintained high public trust throughout the pandemic, the **"mink scandal"** was a notable controversial episode in the country's COVID-19 response.

In November 2020, the Danish government ordered the culling of the country's entire mink population, numbering around 17 million, due to concerns about a mutated strain of the virus that could potentially reduce the effectiveness of COVID-19 vaccines. The decision was made hastily and without the necessary legal framework in place, **leading to significant public outcry and political fallout**.

The scandal highlighted a lack of clear communication and coordination between government agencies, the decision to cull the minks was announced without adequate preparation or consideration of the logistical and ethical implications. This led to confusion and resistance from mink farmers and the public, **undermining trust in the government's handling of the pandemic**. Additionally, **the "mink scandal" raised questions about the transparency and accountability of the decision-making process**. The lack of scientific evidence and risk assessment to support the decision, along with the absence of a clear plan for compensating affected farmers, further exacerbated the controversy.

2.1.4 Good practices and lessons learned

Denmark's experience in managing the COVID-19 pandemic offers a wealth of lessons learned that can inform future pandemic preparedness and response strategies.

Advanced digital health infrastructure

One of the most significant best practices highlighted by Denmark's response is the critical role of **digital infrastructure** in pandemic management. The country's advanced digital systems facilitated data-driven decision-making, efficient contact tracing, and the smooth rollout of vaccinations. The integration of test results into the national online healthcare

portal, *Sundhed.dk*, and the use of digital solutions exemplify the potential of digital tools in controlling the spread of infectious diseases. Investing in and leveraging digital infrastructure can enhance the effectiveness of future pandemic responses, both in Denmark and globally.

High public trust

The importance of public trust and transparent communication is another key lesson learned from Denmark's experience. The high level of public trust in the Danish government and health authorities enabled widespread compliance with guidelines and vaccination programs. Building and maintaining public trust through transparent, timely, and clear communication is essential for the successful implementation of pandemic response measures, and the acceptance of restrictions even in the absence of mandatory enforcement. It underscores the value of **fostering a sense of community and shared responsibility**.

Public-private collaboration and partnerships

Denmark's pandemic response was marked by a successful collaboration between public and private stakeholders, exemplified by initiatives like **Test Center Denmark**, which significantly boosted the country's testing capacity. This centre was created through a unique collaboration between the government, the Danish regions, hospitals, the Novo Nordisk Foundation, and Novo Nordisk A/S. Another example is the "Columna Flow Pandemic Control" solution developed by the company Systematic in collaboration with Danish health authorities as a tool for handling and following up on contact tracing activities during epidemics and pandemics. This digital framework enabled close monitoring of the virus's spread and timely responses to local outbreaks. Additionally, the **"Denmark helps Denmark"** campaign further highlighted this collaborative spirit, with Danish companies producing personal protective equipment (PPE), such as LEGO which produced visors for healthcare workers, and various private companies which collaborated on producing hand sanitizers. These successful public-private collaborations not only met immediate needs but also underscore the value of investing in such partnerships for future pandemic preparedness and health crisis response.

Integrated healthcare system

The decentralized structure of Denmark's healthcare system, with collaboration across different levels of government, offers insights into the importance of **coordinated and integrated healthcare responses**. The establishment of wards for COVID-19 patients and the reallocation of clinical personnel helped prevent the overburdening of hospitals and ensured sufficient resources for managing the pandemic. This experience highlights the opportunity to invest in and strengthen **decentralized healthcare systems** to enhance future pandemic preparedness and response capabilities.

2.1.5 Main highlights from interview with senior policymakers

The interview with a senior adviser at the Danish Medicines Agency (DMA), department of Medical Devices, highlighted several key takeaways regarding Denmark's pandemic preparedness and response:

- **Management of protective supplies:** initially, Denmark lacked adequate stockpiles of basic protective supplies like masks and gloves, revealing gaps in pre-pandemic preparedness. However, the DMA had procedures for issuing derogations for medicines and medical devices, which proved crucial during the crisis. To address the shortage, the respondent's team expanded from five to ten members, focusing extensively on preventing illegal medical devices, such as those with fake European Conformity (CE) marks, from entering the country.
- **Robust digital infrastructure supported the government's response:** technological solutions like vaccine passports and a tracing app were swiftly developed and deployed, enabling close monitoring of the situation while informing decision-making about adjusting restrictions accordingly. Denmark's vaccination campaign was highly successful, rather than mandating vaccinations, the government differentiated restrictions based on vaccination status, encouraging uptake without enforcement.
- **Future preparedness:** Denmark has taken significant steps to prepare for future health crises, the country has established a stock database to ensure better preparedness for future needs and has increased collaboration with sister agencies. Additionally, the National Operative Staff (NOST) under the police has been created to handle various crises, including pandemics.

2.2 France

National health system in a nutshell

France's national health system is centralized and based on a social health insurance model, with a strong role for the state and regional health agencies managing healthcare provision, particularly hospital care. Health spending in France is higher than the EU average, reaching 12.3% of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in 2021, driven by substantial public spending during the COVID-19 pandemic. The government is implementing measures to address shortages of general practitioners leading to "medical deserts" in underserved areas and improve access to

2.2.1 Key measures and strategies

Lockdown measures

The initial response during the first wave, which peaked in March and April 2020, included a **full national lockdown**, which was deemed necessary to prevent the healthcare system from being overwhelmed. This lockdown involved the closure of all schools, universities, and non-essential public places. The government imposed strict social restrictions, including the requirement for written justification to leave one's residence, with fines for non-compliance.

The lockdown was progressively lifted between May and June 2020, but the economic and social costs were significant.

During the second wave, which began in the fall of 2020, the government adopted a more nuanced approach, balancing health needs with socio-economic considerations. **Localized restrictions**, such as night curfews in major cities, were implemented to control the spread of the virus while minimizing economic disruption. A **second national lockdown** was announced in November 2020, but this time, schools remained open, and more flexibility was allowed for work activities.

Public health strategies

In addition to lockdown measures, France implemented a range of public health strategies to control the spread of the virus. Initially, there were shortages of masks and tests, but the government quickly ramped up production and secured imports. Testing capacity was expanded, and PCR tests were made free of charge and available without a prescription. The use of face masks became compulsory in all closed public spaces and later extended to outdoor places in most of the French territory.

The government also focused on **improving the coordination and capacity of the healthcare system**. The emergency '*White Plan*' was launched early in the pandemic to reorganize hospital care and spare capacity for the influx of COVID-19 patients. The need to maintain a certain level of hospital care locally favoured the collaboration between public and private hospitals, which are normally competitors.

Telemedicine was also expanded to monitor patients at home and reduce hospital admissions. A new application, **Covidom**, was launched by the Parisian hospitals in collaboration with ambulatory physicians to monitor Covid-19 patients and their contacts at home. This application is now freely available to all physicians and hospitals in the Ile-de-France region, and being expanded to other French regions.

Economic support

The government's economic response to the pandemic was comprehensive and aimed at supporting both the French economy and its citizens. The key measure introduced was the **generalization of a temporary 'partial unemployment allowance'** for all those who could not continue working or not fully, with the cost entirely supported by the state. Firms and self-employed professionals were allowed to delay their payments of social and fiscal charges, a measure aiming at preventing massive layoffs by shifting charges from employers to the public budget. In May 2020, a second medium-term support plan was adopted with the objective of preserving production capacity. State-guaranteed loans were provided to support strategic economic sectors particularly hit by the sanitary restrictions, such as aviation, vehicle construction, wineries, tourism, and culture. In early September 2020, a strategic longer-term plan for economic recovery (*France Relance*) was announced with a fiscal package of €100 billion, to support innovative projects for ecological transition, green technologies, productivity improvement, and territorial and social cohesion.

2.2.2 Outcomes and impact

The COVID-19 pandemic has had profound and multifaceted impacts on France, which can be broadly categorized into health, economic, and social dimensions.

Health impact

As of mid-November 2020, France had one of the highest rates of prevalence in Europe, with more than 2 million COVID-19 cases (around 32 reported cases per 1000 inhabitants). The first wave of the pandemic saw a rapid increase in cases and hospitalizations. The focus on hospital-centred care led to the neglect of other health and care needs, the French Public Health Agency observed a significant drop in medical consumption for non-COVID-19 patients, and a rise in mental health issues.

Economic Impact

The economic impact of the COVID-19 pandemic in France has been severe. Despite extensive economic support measures, the social security deficit for 2020 was the highest in history, and the economic impact of the pandemic remained severe. The lockdown measures implemented during the first wave led to significant job losses. In September 2020, it was estimated that 305,600 jobs have been lost since the beginning of the year. Moreover, low-wage earners and young people suffered far worse than others in terms of COVID-19-related job losses in 2020, and the poorest part of the population accumulated debt while the higher income groups have been saving.

Social Impact

The lockdown measures caused significant disruptions in education and social life. The closure of schools and universities led to a shift to online teaching, which exacerbated educational inequalities. The lockdown also had a significant impact on mental health, with an alarming increase in anxiety and depressive disorders in France, affecting disproportionately the most vulnerable populations.

The government's response to the pandemic also had social implications. The lack of consultation and transparency in the decision-making process, as well as inconsistent communication from the government, weakened public trust in the measures put forward.

2.2.3 Shortcomings and challenges

France's response to the COVID-19 pandemic revealed several shortcomings and challenges that hindered the effectiveness of its measures and strategies.

Preparedness and initial response

One of the most significant shortcomings in France's response to the COVID-19 pandemic was the **lack of preparedness**. The country experienced a gradual decline in the priority given to pandemic preparedness over the past decade, following criticisms of the management of the H1N1 influenza. This led to a **reduction in national strategic reserves**

of masks and other protective equipment, which, coupled with the transfer of responsibility for storing protective materials to individual healthcare facilities and self-employed physicians, left many healthcare professionals ill-equipped to protect themselves and their patients. The initial response to the pandemic was also **slow and reactive**. The government was unprepared for the rapid spread of the virus and struggled to implement effective **preventive measures**.

Governance and decision-making

The **top-down, centralized health governance** structure in France, piloted directly by the government with the support of a scientific committee, overlooked local situations and the significant variations between regions in terms of local epidemiological situations, healthcare needs, workforce, and care configuration. Decision-making at the local level was severely restricted, with the State Council ruling in April 2020 that municipalities and local authorities were not allowed to take any decisions different from the national emergency legislation. The centralized decision-making process, while allowing for quick national measures, **lacked consultation and transparency**, leading to criticism and a loss of public trust. Improving cooperation between health actors at central and local levels, with greater **participatory decision-making** is key for future pandemic preparedness and response.

Public communication and trust

The government's communication regarding the COVID-19 pandemic oscillated between dramatization and trivialization, instead of factual and transparent communication. This **inconsistency** weakened public trust in the measures put forward and undermined the effectiveness of the government's response to the pandemic, delaying the widespread adoption of masks as a preventive measure, and leading to confusion and delays in the widespread adoption of testing as a preventive measure.

Poor communication on the measures introduced and the arbitrary nature of some restrictions, particularly concerning visits to nursing homes, were highly criticized. The aftermath of the first lockdown was characterized by demands for greater accountability for the government's actions during the first wave of the pandemic.

Healthcare coordination and capacity

The coordination between different parts of the French healthcare system was weak, the pandemic highlighted **structural weaknesses** in health governance, including the **bureaucracy** in the relations between the Ministry of Health and its local organs, the shortcomings of these organs for supporting local logistics and supply, and the difficulties in articulating health and social care policies at the local level.

The focus on **hospital-centred care** led to the neglect of other health and care needs, including the elderly. The lack of coordination between nursing homes, hospitals, and primary care providers contributed to the high death toll during the first wave.

Additionally, the testing strategy was initially ineffective, with **limited capacity** and a lack of systematic testing. The lack of effective tracing and isolation measures contributed to the need for ongoing restrictive measures, including the second lockdown in November 2020.

2.2.4 Good practices and lessons learned

The COVID-19 pandemic, while presenting significant challenges, also offered valuable insights that can guide future policymaking and enhance the resilience of the healthcare system and society.

Comprehensive economic support

France's comprehensive economic support measures were instrumental in mitigating the economic impact of the pandemic. They helped protect jobs, prevent massive lay-offs, and support strategic economic sectors. The France Relance plan, with its substantial fiscal package, further highlighted the importance of **long-term economic recovery strategies** that focus on innovation, ecological transition, and social cohesion. This good practice underscores the value of **integrating economic support with public health measures to ensure a holistic response to pandemics.**

Public-private collaboration

The public–private cooperation intensified, removing traditional borders and boundaries between health professionals. This **collaboration between public and private hospitals**, facilitated by the emergency 'White Plan,' was a notable good practice in France's response. It helped reorganize hospital care and spare capacity for the influx of COVID-19 patients, demonstrating the importance of integrated resources and coordinated efforts across different healthcare providers.

Strengthening healthcare infrastructure and coordination

The pandemic highlighted the need for a well-prepared and coordinated healthcare system. Initial shortages of masks and tests, along with the structural weaknesses in healthcare governance, underscored the importance of **investing in healthcare infrastructure and supply chains**. Ensuring adequate stockpiles of PPE and improving the coordination across the healthcare system are essential for future pandemic preparedness.

The pandemic also emphasized the need for a more decentralized and integrated approach to healthcare management, allowing for better local logistics and supply support. Enhancing public health capacity and improving the working conditions of health workers through **structural reforms** will enable France to better manage future health crises and ensure a more effective response. This includes investing in surveillance systems, testing capabilities, and contact tracing mechanisms.

Investing in telemedicine and digital health

The pandemic highlighted the resilience and innovation capacity of healthcare actors in France, particularly through the **accelerated adoption of more flexible and online care provision**. The success of applications like Covidom shows the potential of telemedicine in reducing hospital admissions and managing patient care remotely, especially during health crises. It highlights the potential of digital health to transform healthcare delivery. France must continue to invest in digital health and expand telemedicine, ensuring that these innovations are **generalized and integrated** into the healthcare system.

2.2.5 Main highlights from interview with senior policymakers

The interviews with three senior policymakers, including the President of COVARS (the French Committee for Monitoring and Anticipating Health Risks), a prominent member of the Académie Nationale de Médecine, and the Head of the Health Crisis Centre at the French Ministry of Health, provided invaluable insights into the strengths and weaknesses of France's pandemic response. These discussions highlighted several critical areas for improvement and best practices that can inform future pandemic response strategies.

Lessons learned from the COVID-19 pandemic

- **The need for a more agile and adaptable health system:** one of the recurring themes among interviewees was the complexity of France's public health system, which "may have contributed to some initial slowness in responding to the pandemic". This complexity often hindered the swift implementation of necessary measures, and streamlining and simplifying the system could improve responsiveness in future crises.
- **The importance of healthcare system capacity and the need for scalable resources:** "the limited capacity of the healthcare system to handle the surge in patients were key factors in the decision to implement a full lockdown", the experience underscored the necessity of having a robust and flexible healthcare infrastructure that can quickly scale up to meet the demands of a pandemic.
- **The need for formal structures or mechanisms for international decision-making:** While international scientific collaboration was strong, informal partnerships often did not translate into unified international decisions, leading to delays or fragmented responses. Additionally, shared budgets among countries proved to be clearly beneficial.
- **The need for a robust decision-making framework:** the availability of real-time data and digital tools during the pandemic was unprecedented and highly beneficial for epidemiological monitoring. However, "the effective use of these data requires not just collection and analysis, but also decision-making," with the challenge being how data can be used to inform policies that lead to practical and impactful outcomes. "Scientists can propose actions, but the final decisions lie with policymakers".
- **The need for sustained efforts** to maintain and enhance pandemic preparedness and response capabilities: one of the respondents raised the concern of "post-pandemic amnesia", where the lessons learned and the sense of urgency fade as the pandemic recedes, potentially leaving the system unprepared for future threats.

Interviewees' insights about PAIR technologies

PANPOC and PANRISK were identified as tools that can significantly support governments in tracking and responding to future pandemics. However, "it is essential that these technologies are approved and validated" to ensure their effectiveness and reliability. Regarding PANPOC, the importance of monitoring specific virus groups for potential future pandemics was emphasized. The interviews highlighted three virus groups, including

influenza viruses, coronaviruses, and poxviruses. This proactive approach is essential for early detection and response to emerging threats.

According to the respondents, PANPOC could be integrated into France's existing health surveillance systems, such as *Système d'Information de DEPistage (SI-DEP)*, to enhance the country's ability to quickly detect and respond to emerging respiratory viruses. The challenge lies in ensuring the interconnectivity of PANPOC with existing information systems and obtaining necessary authorizations for data linkage. Likewise, it was argued that PANRISK could be integrated into France's crisis management framework, providing predictive analytics to support decision-making processes and allow for proactive measures. The challenge would entail the accuracy and reliability of the model's predictions and integrating it with existing decision-making structures.

2.3 Latvia

National health system in a nutshell

Latvia's national health system is centralized with a strong role for the state. The system is based on a tax-funded model, with universal coverage guaranteed by the constitution. However, the benefits package is not as comprehensive as in many other EU countries, leading to high out-of-pocket spending, particularly on outpatient pharmaceuticals. The health system faces challenges such as an aging population, a shortage of nurses, and a significant urban-rural divide in access to healthcare services.

2.3.1 Key measures and strategies

Lockdown measures

Latvia declared a state of emergency on 12 March 2020, which included a range of restrictions to control the spread of COVID-19. Schools and universities were closed, public gatherings were banned, and non-essential businesses were shut down. International travel was restricted, and a curfew and mandatory quarantine for individuals returning from high-risk countries were imposed. Over the course of the pandemic, three significant lockdowns were implemented. These measures were notably effective during the first wave, preventing severe shortages in personal protective equipment (PPE) and earning public approval. However, **the response was hindered by a lack of a comprehensive National Civil Protection Plan and detailed disaster management protocols.**

Public health strategies

Latvia's public health strategies focused on increasing testing capacity, contact tracing, and ensuring adequate healthcare resources. The government established a centralized system for coordinating the pandemic response, with the Centre for Disease Prevention and Control playing a key role. Testing was made widely available, and contact tracing was implemented to identify and isolate infected individuals. Before the crisis, Latvia's healthcare expenditure per capita was among the lowest in the EU. The government responded by increasing health sector funding, raising medical staff wages, and worked to secure PPE and other medical supplies to ensure the safety of healthcare workers. While these measures improved

capacity, initial delays in vaccination efforts, logistical hurdles, and public scepticism highlighted persistent systemic issues.

Economic support

To cushion the pandemic's economic impact, Latvia introduced a suite of financial support mechanisms, including downtime compensation for businesses, wage subsidies for employees, tax relief measures and aid for vulnerable groups. Although GDP contracted by 3.6% in 2020, the economy demonstrated resilience with a strong recovery in 2021, driven by increased consumer spending, export growth, and public investment. The government's **pro-investment initiatives**, such as the "Green Channel," attracted foreign direct investment, which reached 5.6% of GDP in the first nine months of 2021.

Nevertheless, the support measures were seen as proportional to the crisis, helping to stabilise the labour market and underpin economic resilience.

2.3.2 Outcomes and impact

The COVID-19 pandemic had a profound impact on Latvia, reshaping the country's health and economy systems. These effects underscored existing vulnerabilities while also prompting significant reforms and adaptations across various sectors.

Health impact

The pandemic placed immense strain on Latvia's underfunded healthcare system, with life expectancy dropping from 75.5 years in 2020 to 73.1 years in 2021 due to excess mortality. However, the country managed to keep the situation relatively under control. As of early 2022, Latvia's cumulative confirmed COVID-19 death rate per million people was 2,477, which was close to the EU average of 2,044. This relatively moderate death rate, considering the limited healthcare resources, shows the effectiveness of the public health measures implemented.

The crisis prompted overdue reforms, including greater investment in healthcare infrastructure, higher wages for medical professionals, and the adoption of digital health strategies, offering hope for sustained improvements in the sector.

Economic Impact

The pandemic tested Latvia's small and open economy, revealing vulnerabilities but also its capacity for resilience. Economic contraction was relatively moderate compared to other EU countries, with GDP recovering in 2021 through robust export performance and strategic public investments supported by the EU Recovery and Resilience Plan. Despite these positive trends, the labour market suffered, with unemployment rising, and long-term joblessness threatening to increase structural unemployment. Wage growth persisted due to labour shortages and efforts by employers to retain skilled workers. Despite the government's economic measures, challenges such as low productivity and regional labour market disparities remain significant obstacles to sustainable growth.

Social Impact

The pandemic deepened existing social inequalities, disproportionately affecting low-income and rural communities. The lockdown measures caused significant disruptions in education and social life, the shift to online teaching exacerbated educational inequalities, while the shift toward remote work and digital solutions highlighted a need for greater investment in digital infrastructure and for addressing the digital divide.

The lockdown also had a significant impact on mental health, with an increase in anxiety and depressive disorders. Trust in the government initially rose during the first wave but waned as subsequent waves revealed gaps in preparedness and governance. Vaccination efforts were hampered by individualistic cultural values and institutional mistrust, although progress was eventually achieved. Public sentiment reflected both **resilience and frustration**, underscoring the importance of cohesive governance and social solidarity in navigating public health crises.

2.3.3 Shortcomings and challenges

The COVID-19 pandemic exposed several shortcomings and challenges in Latvia's crisis management and institutional frameworks.

Preparedness and initial response

Latvia's response to the COVID-19 pandemic revealed significant gaps in its preparedness for large-scale crises, notably **the absence of a comprehensive National Civil Protection Plan** and a robust disaster management framework. While the existing Epidemiological Safety Law provided a legal foundation for addressing infectious diseases, it lacked provisions for coordinating a complex, multi-agency response to a pandemic of this magnitude. Legal uncertainties regarding emergency measures and the absence of clearly defined inter-agency protocols further impeded the efficiency of the initial response. Delays in vaccine procurement and distribution added to these challenges, emphasising the need for stronger logistical frameworks and strategic operational planning.

Governance and decision-making

The absence of a centralised framework led to **fragmented decision-making** and responses among municipalities and state institutions, as well as **weak inter-institutional coordination**, resulting in administrative inefficiencies.

During the second and third waves of the pandemic, the government failed to learn from earlier mistakes, with decentralized planning and insufficient focus on cohesive policy implementation. The lack of regulatory effectiveness assessments and adaptability to evolving circumstances impeded efficient management. Despite these challenges, Latvia managed to avoid complete functional disruptions, but significant gaps in strategic leadership persisted.

Public communication and trust

Co-funded by the
European Union

Public trust in the government fluctuated significantly during the pandemic. While initial responses garnered some support due to lower infection rates, inconsistent communication strategies, public scandals related to vaccination policies, and slow adaptation to societal concerns led to sharp declines in trust. The “infodemic” fuelled by misinformation and geopolitical disinformation further strained the public’s confidence in authorities, especially during contentious periods like the introduction of mandatory vaccination policies.

Healthcare coordination and capacity

Latvia’s **underfunded healthcare system**, already stretched thin before the crisis, struggled to cope with the pandemic’s demands. Shortages of medical personnel, inadequate infrastructure, and over-reliance on household out-of-pocket expenses underscored **systemic weaknesses**. The bureaucracy in the relations between the Ministry of Health and its local organs, the structural weaknesses of these organs for supporting local logistics and supply, and the difficulties in articulating health and social care policies at the local level were significant challenges. Although the crisis prompted investments in infrastructure and wage increases for medical staff, fragmented coordination among healthcare institutions and inadequate rural healthcare access remained significant challenges.

2.3.4 Good practices and lessons learned

Strengthening healthcare infrastructure and coordination

The COVID-19 pandemic exposed significant gaps in Latvia’s healthcare infrastructure, particularly in rural areas and staffing shortages. The crisis spurred improvements in infrastructure, including better-equipped medical facilities and enhanced remuneration for healthcare workers. These developments highlighted the importance of **building a cohesive healthcare system** with strengthened primary care services and centralised crisis management to ensure resilience in the face of future public health threats.

The pandemic also exposed the need for investment in healthcare supply chains. Latvia responded by securing PPE and other medical supplies, while making significant investments in healthcare facilities and medical equipment, bolstering the capacity of the healthcare system. Ensuring adequate stockpiles of protective equipment, improving coordination between different parts of the healthcare system, and continued sustainable investment in these areas are essential for future pandemic preparedness and response.

Investing in pandemic preparedness

The lack of a valid National Civil Protection Plan and an effective disaster risk management system at the onset of the pandemic highlighted the need for better preparedness in Latvia. Investing in pandemic preparedness plans and disaster risk management systems is crucial for future health crises. Strengthening collaboration among institutions, creating a unified structure for emergency management, and prioritising evidence-based policymaking are essential improvements. These measures, combined with strengthened communication

strategies and professionalised public messaging, foster trust in governance, encourage cooperation from the public, and ensure a more effective response to future emergencies.

Investing in telemedicine and digital health

Latvia leveraged digital health initiatives to support its pandemic response. The country's rapid adoption of digital health technologies during the pandemic significantly improved healthcare access and continuity. The successful implementation of initiatives such as contact tracing apps and telemedicine services enhanced the efficiency and accessibility of healthcare services. Digital tools like electronic prescriptions and patient portals expanded access to essential services, particularly in rural areas. The integration of electronic health records and further investment in digital health infrastructure are fundamental for optimising these advancements and ensuring their sustainability in routine healthcare provision and in future pandemic responses.

2.3.5 Main highlights from interview with senior policymakers

To build on the background analysis conducted on Latvia's COVID-19 pandemic preparedness and response, an in-depth interview was conducted with the Director of the Public Health Department at Latvia's Ministry of Health. This conversation aimed to gain valuable insights from a key figure actively involved in managing the country's public health strategies during the pandemic, offering a firsthand perspective on the challenges, successes, and lessons learned from the field.

Lessons learned from the COVID-19 pandemic

- **The need for a robust and integrated pandemic response framework**, for which the respondent highlighted the value of close personal relationships between ministries and sectors, which enabled rapid decision-making during the pandemic. While effective in a small country like Latvia, formalising this collaboration could enhance its scalability and ensure continuity in larger-scale crises.
- **The importance of leveraging digital tools in public health:** the pandemic drove Latvia's adoption of new digital technologies, including a digital reporting system and a vaccination registry, which improved real-time data collection, streamlined epidemiological surveillance, and facilitated vaccine monitoring and real-time stock management. The respondent noted that integrating these technologies into routine healthcare practices would be vital for strengthening pandemic response capacity.
- **Addressing vaccine hesitancy and trust in public institutions:** vaccine hesitancy was a significant challenge, particularly among the Russian-speaking population, some of whom preferred non-EU vaccines. "This lack of trust extended to the scientists who were advising the government." It was emphasised that tackling historical scepticism and implementing targeted communication strategies could improve vaccination uptake in future public health campaigns.
- **Expanding the One Health approach:** Latvia demonstrated significant progress in adopting the One Health approach. This entailed joint zoonotic disease reporting,

wastewater monitoring, and addressing antimicrobial resistance. Building on these efforts could further strengthen holistic response to future health challenges.

Interviewee's insights about PAIR technologies

Although the respondent did not explicitly mention PANPOC or PANRISK during the interview, they underscored the vital role of digital tools and predictive technologies in strengthening pandemic preparedness and response. They identified **AI and predictive modelling** as key areas of investment, enhancing scenario planning and data analysis. They added that “the systems must be user-friendly, fast, and easy to integrate with local systems like our e-health and epidemiological surveillance systems”, while also being **interoperable** with EU and WHO systems to avoid duplicating data entry across platforms.

2.4 Italy

National health system in a nutshell

Italy's national health system is decentralized, with a strong role for the state in financing and overseeing healthcare provision. The system provides universal coverage to all residents, but there are significant regional disparities in access and quality of care. The health system faces challenges such as an aging population, a shortage of healthcare professionals, and a high level of out-of-pocket expenditure, particularly for specialist care and pharmaceuticals.

2.4.1 Key measures and strategies

Italy was one of the first European countries to be severely affected by the COVID-19 pandemic. On 31 January 2020, Italy's Council of Ministers declared a six-month state of emergency in response to the health risks posed by the outbreak.

Lockdown measures

During the first wave of COVID-19 in spring 2020, Italy imposed a **nationwide lockdown** beginning 11 March, **which was among the strictest in Europe**. It included the closure of all non-essential businesses, schools and universities, as well as restrictions on movement and bans on public gatherings. Travel was limited to essential purposes only, and a curfew was imposed. The lockdown effectively curbed the virus's spread, and these measures were gradually eased starting in May 2020, supported by mass testing and early vaccination efforts, but some restrictions remained in place to prevent a resurgence of the virus.

Italy's lockdown measures during the first wave were widely acknowledged for their decisiveness, yet criticism centred on the government's lack of early preparedness and coordination.

The second wave in autumn 2020 prompted a reintroduction of restrictions. The government implemented a regional approach, classifying areas into yellow, orange, and red zones, with the strictest measures applied to red zones. These classifications were based on weekly risk assessments using 21 epidemiological indicators. While this tailored approach improved response efforts, it also exposed inconsistencies in enforcement and outcomes. Gradual

easing of restrictions helped avoid a sudden resurgence of cases, emphasizing the need for robust monitoring systems, widespread testing, and effective public awareness campaigns to manage transitions effectively.

Public health strategies

Italy's public health response to COVID-19 showcased both strengths and challenges. The healthcare system faced **significant strain**, particularly in the hardest-hit regions like Lombardy. The government responded by increasing intensive care capacity, converting existing facilities into COVID-19 wards, and constructing new temporary hospitals. The military was also deployed to assist with logistics and patient transport.

Public health strategies included nationwide lockdowns and region-based restrictions, mass testing, contact tracing, and a comprehensive vaccination campaign. Telemedicine solutions and innovative digital tools, such as the Green Pass for vaccination and testing certification, were introduced to enable a safer reopening and enhance public compliance. Italy's vaccination campaign coordinated by the Ministry of Health began in late December 2020, following the approval of the first COVID-19 vaccines. The government prioritized healthcare workers, elderly individuals, and those with underlying health conditions. The campaign, though successful in its later stages, faced early hurdles such as logistical bottlenecks and vaccine hesitancy, and the government launched a public awareness campaign to encourage vaccination.

While these public health strategies and measures helped address short-term needs, the pandemic shed light on the **urgent necessity of systemic reforms**.

Economic support

The COVID-19 pandemic had profound economic implications for Italy, exposing vulnerabilities and prompting a series of urgent financial interventions. Italy's economy, already strained by years of austerity and cost-containment measures, faced severe disruptions due to prolonged lockdowns and the shutdown of non-essential sectors, which led to significant economic contraction.

In response, the Italian government implemented a range of economic support measures aimed at mitigating the pandemic's impact. These included financial assistance for businesses, provisions to ensure liquidity, and initiatives to support households. Decrees such as "Cura Italia" (17 March 2020) and "Rilancio" (13 May 2020) allocated resources to sustain the healthcare system, protect employment, and bolster business continuity.

Gradual reopening from May 2020, under strict health protocols, allowed the economy to regain some momentum. **Investments in digital tools and telemedicine emerged as areas of focus**, aligning with broader efforts to modernize infrastructure and improve service delivery. Despite these measures, regional disparities in economic resilience and healthcare capacity underscored the **need for equitable resource allocation and long-term systemic reforms**. Italy's economic recovery proved the importance of sustained investment in healthcare infrastructure and workforce development.

2.4.2 Outcomes and impact

The Italian crisis provoked by COVID-19 is the most serious event in Italian history after World War II; it is a national human, health, and economic tragedy.

Health impact

Italy faced one of the deadliest outbreaks globally, with a 9% mortality rate by the end of 2020. Lombardy, the epicentre, experienced a +118% surge in excess mortality during the first wave, straining hospitals in the north, which faced acute shortages of ICU beds and supplies. Healthcare workers endured significant challenges, with high infection rates and burnout adding to the crisis.

Routine medical services and elective surgeries were disrupted, worsening outcomes for non-COVID conditions. Mental health effects were profound, with widespread anxiety, depression, and stress exacerbated by lockdowns and economic uncertainty, underscoring the need for psychological support and robust community interventions during health crisis.

Economic Impact

The economic fallout was **severe**, with Italy's GDP contracting by 9% in 2020. Public health expenditure rose by 5.2%, yet unemployment reached 10%, with youth unemployment at 31%. Government measures, such as layoffs suspensions and short-time work programs, mitigated immediate job losses but masked deeper structural vulnerabilities. Longstanding economic challenges, including stagnant incomes and regional disparities, became more pronounced. Italy's real per capita income dropped to under United States Dollar (USD) 34,000 in 2022, down from USD 41,000 in 2008, making it **the only G7 nation with declining living standards** over that period. The pandemic revealed the need for robust economic recovery plans and equitable resource distribution to address systemic weaknesses and build resilience against future crises.

Social Impact

The pandemic **profoundly reshaped Italian society**, disrupting daily life and exacerbating pre-existing inequalities. Lockdowns and restrictions isolated individuals, disrupted social cohesion, and disproportionately affected vulnerable groups such as the elderly and low-income households. Educational disparities widened as students in underprivileged areas, particularly in southern Italy, struggled with access to online learning. Local traditions and communal activities were curtailed, weakening social bonds. Women bore disproportionate burdens, balancing domestic responsibilities with professional challenges. However, acts of solidarity and mutual aid also emerged, showcasing community resilience. These efforts highlighted the importance of strengthening social infrastructure to address inequality, support caregiving roles, and promote digital inclusion.

2.4.3 Shortcomings and challenges

Preparedness and initial response

Co-funded by the
European Union

Italy's initial response to the pandemic was hindered by a lack of preparedness, stemming from outdated pandemic plans that had not been revised or implemented effectively. Stockpiles of personal protective equipment were insufficient, testing infrastructure was underdeveloped, and early warning systems were not adequately utilized. These gaps delayed the identification of cases and the implementation of containment measures, allowing the virus to spread unchecked, particularly in the densely populated northern regions.

As the initial response to the pandemic was characterized by delays and inconsistencies, vaccine distribution faced logistical hurdles such as fragmented supply chains, limited cold storage facilities, and disparities in regional administration. This led to confusion and a delayed public response, contributing to the rapid spread of the virus.

Governance and decision-making

Italy's decentralized healthcare system, with significant autonomy granted to its regions, complicated the pandemic response. The pandemic revealed systemic vulnerabilities within Italy's healthcare and governance frameworks, regional governments had varying levels of capacity and resources, resulting in inconsistent approaches to containment, resource allocation, and policy implementation.

Centralized decision-making was further impeded by political conflicts and fragmented authority, leading to delays in enforcing cohesive national policies. The lack of a unified national strategy and coordination between the central government and regional authorities hindered the effectiveness of the response.

Public communication and trust

Public communication during the pandemic was plagued by confusion, inconsistency, and a lack of transparency. Early government messages downplayed the severity of the virus, leading to public complacency. Frequent changes to restrictions and vague explanations for policy decisions eroded trust in government actions. A particularly damaging incident occurred when lockdown plans were prematurely leaked, prompting mass migrations from northern to southern regions and likely accelerating the virus's spread. Furthermore, efforts to combat misinformation and effectively reach vulnerable populations were inadequate, underscoring the urgent need for a unified, clear, and inclusive communication strategy.

Healthcare coordination and capacity

The healthcare system faced unprecedented strain during the pandemic, revealing deep systemic weaknesses. Hospitals in northern Italy were quickly overwhelmed due to the surge in cases, facing acute shortages of ICU beds, ventilators, and healthcare workers. Years of underfunding and austerity measures had eroded the system's capacity, leaving it ill-equipped to handle a crisis of this magnitude. Regional disparities in healthcare resources further exacerbated the crisis, as southern regions struggled with weaker infrastructure and limited capacity. Testing and contact tracing efforts were uneven across regions, hampered by inconsistent strategies and resource allocations.

Coordination between hospitals and community-based care was inadequate, resulting in overcrowded facilities and insufficient management of non-critical COVID-19 patients.

2.4.4 Good practices and lessons learned

The COVID-19 pandemic served as a **wake-up call** for Italy, revealing both vulnerabilities and opportunities for improvement. By learning from these experiences, Italy has the chance to emerge stronger, with a more equitable, resilient, and sustainable health system.

Increased healthcare capacity

Italy responded to the urgent need for increased healthcare capacity by **rapidly expanding intensive care capacity**, converting existing facilities into COVID-19 wards, and constructing new temporary hospitals. The military was also deployed to assist with logistics and patient transport, helping to alleviate the strain on the healthcare system. Yet the COVID-19 pandemic highlighted the **necessity to overhaul Italy's public health system**, particularly in addressing regional disparities and ensuring adequate preparedness for future crises.

Strengthening public health coordination and integration

The pandemic exposed significant gaps in Italy's healthcare workforce and infrastructure. Investment in healthcare infrastructure, workforce training, and recruitment is crucial for future pandemic preparedness. The crisis underscored the importance of a **coordinated approach to health emergencies**, including stockpiling essential supplies, investing in preventive care, and strengthening community health networks. Future plans must prioritise integrating public health with community and digital health solutions to improve access, particularly in underserved areas.

Investing in telemedicine and digital health

Italy leveraged digital health initiatives to support its pandemic response. The government developed contact tracing apps and expanded telemedicine services to provide remote consultations and reduce the burden on healthcare facilities and maintain healthcare delivery during lockdowns. Teleconsultations, remote monitoring, and digital prescriptions became vital tools, particularly for managing chronic conditions and providing care in underserved areas.

Investing in nationwide digital health infrastructure, training healthcare providers in telemedicine, expanding digital literacy among patients, and developing standardized reimbursement policies will ensure long-term benefits from these advancements.

Addressing regional disparities and social inequalities

A key lesson is that COVID-19 exacerbated pre-existing social inequalities in Italy, disproportionately impacting vulnerable groups such as low-income families, the elderly, and residents of southern regions. Southern Italy faced heightened challenges during the pandemic, building on pre-existing fragility in healthcare, education, and infrastructure.

Territorial disparities, referred to as a "citizenship gap" in access to fundamental rights, grew even wider, undermining social cohesion and economic recovery.

Female employment, already among the lowest in Europe, suffered a further decline during the pandemic, which intensified the challenges of balancing family and professional responsibilities, exacerbated by a welfare system inadequate in supporting working women. Addressing these inequities requires comprehensive and inclusive social policies that prioritise equitable access to healthcare, education, and digital resources. Stronger social safety nets and targeted investments in marginalised communities are essential to foster resilience.

2.4.5 Main highlights from interview with senior policymakers

Building on the background analysis conducted on Italy's COVID-19 pandemic preparedness and response, an in-depth interview was conducted with an official within the Ministry of Health - General Directorate for animal health and veterinary medicines.

Unlike other stakeholders interviewed, whose discussions primarily focused on the preparation and response of the social and healthcare systems to the pandemic, the respondent's role allowed for **a deeper exploration of zoonotic disease management and the integration of veterinary and public health efforts within the One Health framework** as part of Italy's pandemic preparedness and response.

Lessons learned from the COVID-19 pandemic

- **Lack of risk assessment mechanisms:** processes for recognising and addressing **emerging diseases** were not streamlined, resulting in slower implementation of coordinated measures. "The arrival of COVID-19 caught us unprepared", there was no initial evaluation of which animal species might act as reservoirs or vectors for COVID-19, and surveillance efforts were **reactive** rather than proactive.
- **Lessons from high-risk environments:** the interview emphasised the risks posed by high-density animal farming and the need for better planning and regulation in these environments.
- **Delayed communication and coordination:** key information about COVID-19 cases in mink farms was first received through informal channels rather than official communications, causing delays in response. The absence of timely coordination at both the EU and international levels led to countries acting independently, often with varying strategies and outcomes, highlighting the need for uniform guidelines.
- **One Health approach requires global cooperation:** effective implementation of One Health principles demands investment in low-income countries, focusing on surveillance, biosecurity, and training for those working in high-risk environments.

Interviewee's insights about PAIR technologies

While the respondent did not directly address the PAIR technologies, their insights highlighted **the gaps in technological integration during Italy's pandemic response**, which relied on manual processes. In their opinion, the lack of predictive models and

advanced technological tools, such as AI-driven ones, hindered timeliness and precision in managing zoonotic risks.

2.5 Spain

National health system in a nutshell

Spain's national health system is decentralized, funded primarily through general taxation and offers a comprehensive benefits package. However, there are significant regional disparities in access and quality of care. The health system faces challenges such as an aging population, a shortage of healthcare professionals, and a high level of out-of-pocket expenditure.

2.5.1 Key measures and strategies

Lockdown measures

Spain implemented two **states of alarm** to address the COVID-19 pandemic, each characterised by different approaches to lockdown measures. The first state of alarm, declared on 14 March 2020, introduced a **nationwide, centralised lockdown**. Restrictions were severe, limiting mobility to essential activities, with children disproportionately impacted as they were not permitted outdoor activities. The government extended this state of alarm six times, ultimately ending it on 21 June 2020. The second state of alarm, declared on 25 October 2020, marked a **shift toward co-governance**. It allowed Autonomous Communities to tailor restrictions, including night curfews, perimeter closures, and limits on gatherings. The second lockdown's more flexible, regionally-adapted measures aimed to balance public health needs with local governance, though concerns over legal clarity and fragmented responses persisted. The state of alarm remained in effect until 9 May 2021. To transition from lockdown, Spain implemented a phased "de-escalation" plan, applied asymmetrically across regions based on epidemiological indicators and healthcare capacity.

Public health strategies

Spain implemented a comprehensive set of public health strategies during the COVID-19 pandemic to mitigate transmission and manage the health crisis. Early measures included activating protocols for case detection, surveillance, and contact tracing, coordinated by the Ministry of Health and regional governments. Physical distancing policies and mask mandates were progressively enforced, starting with restrictions on public gatherings and travel, culminating in a nationwide lockdown under the state of alarm. Public communication was a priority, with regular updates, public awareness campaigns, and targeted guidance for high-risk settings such as nursing homes and prisons.

Vaccination was a cornerstone of Spain's COVID-19 response strategy. The Ministry of Health launched a phased, voluntary, and free vaccination campaign on December 27, 2020. Priority groups included residents and workers in assisted-living facilities, healthcare workers, and those with high dependency. The strategy evolved with new evidence, expanding eligibility to children aged 5-11 and incorporating booster doses for specific

groups. By September 2021, Spain achieved 70% full vaccination coverage, marking a significant milestone in its pandemic response.

Economic support

Spain implemented a comprehensive range of economic and social support measures to mitigate the profound financial and social impact, particularly on its most vulnerable populations, as 2.5 million people faced severe poverty and 26% were at risk of poverty or social exclusion.

To address these challenges, the government introduced a **minimum living income** (Ingreso Mínimo Vital) to provide financial stability for struggling households and extended protections for individuals at risk of losing their homes or employment. Temporary restrictions on layoffs were imposed to stabilize the workforce, while extraordinary income support was provided to self-employed individuals and temporary workers traditionally ineligible for unemployment benefits. Targeted assistance was extended to seasonal and agricultural workers, including measures to make unemployment benefits compatible with ongoing work and extended migration permits. Businesses, especially SMEs, received substantial support through a bank guarantee program while employers and self-employed individuals experiencing reduced activity were granted deferrals and exemptions for social security contributions. These initiatives were critical in stabilizing employment and safeguarding the economy during the crisis.

2.5.2 Outcomes and impact

Health impact

COVID-19 had a profound health impact on Spain, with the country experiencing one of the highest mortality rates in Europe during the pandemic. By 2020, nearly 50,000 deaths were reported, with COVID-19 accounting for approximately 15% of all deaths in that year. The pandemic significantly **strained Spain's healthcare infrastructure**, particularly in urban areas like Madrid and Catalonia, where hospitals were overwhelmed during multiple waves. Issues included limited ICU capacity and shortages of medical supplies such as ventilators and protective equipment. Health workers in Spain experienced some of the highest infection rates globally during the early months of the pandemic, further compounding the healthcare system's challenges. Non-COVID medical services faced disruptions, delaying treatment for other health conditions.

Economic impact

The economic impact of COVID-19 in Spain was severe and multifaceted, leading to **one of the most severe recessions in decades**. The pandemic caused widespread disruptions particularly across sectors reliant on mobility and face-to-face interaction, such as tourism, hospitality, and retail. Tourism, a cornerstone of Spain's economy, experienced a near-total collapse, significantly affecting regions heavily dependent on this sector. Lockdown measures and social distancing led to sharp declines in consumer demand and production output. As a result, Spain's GDP contracted by approximately 10-12% in 2020, and

unemployment rates surged to unprecedented levels, with effective unemployment peaking at over 36% during the crisis's height.

The pandemic also exposed Spain's structural economic vulnerabilities, including reliance on SMEs with limited financial reserves and significant public debt. Public finances deteriorated sharply due to declining revenues and increased spending on healthcare and economic relief measures, pushing the national debt above 115% of GDP.

Social impact

Lockdowns and restrictions on movement led to widespread isolation, contributing to a significant **rise in mental health issues** such as anxiety, depression, and stress. Vulnerable populations, including low-income families, the elderly, and those with pre-existing mental health conditions, were disproportionately affected. Children and adolescents faced additional challenges, including the closure of schools and reduced social interaction, which negatively impacted their psychological well-being. Mental health services were overwhelmed, and many struggled to access support during the pandemic's peak. Furthermore, prolonged economic uncertainty exacerbated stress and mental health challenges across all socioeconomic groups.

2.5.3 Shortcomings and challenges

Preparedness and initial response

The primary shortcoming in Spain's management of the pandemic was the **lack of preparedness**, characterized by insufficient stockpiles of personal protective equipment, testing kits, and ventilators. This deficiency exposed significant vulnerabilities in the national healthcare system. Although initial measures were taken as early as January 23, 2020, including the activation of protocols for detection and surveillance following the first confirmed cases, early government messaging understated the risks. This led to complacency and delays in recognizing the severity of the crisis. The national response gained momentum with the declaration of the **state of alarm** on March 14, 2020.

Governance and decision-making

The governance of Spain's pandemic response revealed the challenges of its decentralized political system, which divides healthcare responsibilities among 17 Autonomous Communities. This structure led to significant **inconsistencies** in implementing measures, resource allocation, and data reporting. Initial delays in decision-making and coordination between the central government and regional authorities further exacerbated the crisis. The lack of standardized protocols and the absence of a central data repository made it difficult to manage and compare regional responses effectively. **Political polarization and disputes among parties**, as well as between central and regional governments, hindered the ability to present a unified response. Regional disparities in healthcare infrastructure, staffing, and funding further complicated efforts to manage the pandemic.

Public communication and trust

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Early on, government communication was criticized for delays in providing information, a lack of consistency, and insufficient transparency about mortality and other critical data. Government representatives were criticized for avoiding direct questioning from journalists early in the crisis, undermining transparency. This **eroded confidence** in government actions and measures put forward. Mixed messages, particularly those from different levels of government, compounded public confusion.

Efforts to counter **misinformation** were also insufficient, as citizens struggled with over-information from a variety of sources, including traditional and social media. This highlighted the need for clear and unified communication strategies that aligned with diverse media consumption patterns.

Healthcare coordination and capacity

The Spanish healthcare system, already strained by a decade of budget reductions following the 2008 financial crisis, struggled to cope with the surge in COVID-19 cases. Early in the pandemic, hospitals, especially in Madrid and Catalonia, were overwhelmed, with ICU capacities stretched to the limit. Emergency measures included the expansion of ICU beds, recruitment of healthcare workers, and establishment of temporary field hospitals. However, regional disparities in healthcare capacity and resources created unequal access to care. Testing and contact tracing efforts were inconsistent across regions, reflecting the fragmented nature of the system. Nonetheless, innovative measures such as telemedicine and workforce mobilization helped alleviate some pressures on the system.

2.5.4 Good practices and lessons learned

Healthcare system adaptation

Despite challenges, Spain demonstrated a remarkable **ability to adapt by rapidly scaling up healthcare capacity**, including the conversion of non-medical facilities such as convention centres into emergency hospitals and the mobilization of military resources for logistical support. Additionally, the nationwide vaccination strategy launched in December 2020 was a significant success, well-organized and efficient, leading to high vaccination rates among the population.

Overall, the Spanish healthcare system demonstrated **resilience** by quickly adapting to the surge in patients. Investing in healthcare infrastructure and ensuring adequate stockpiles of medical supplies could better prepare the system for future crises.

Data and evidence-based decision making

Spain established robust systems for collecting and analysing epidemiological data, which were essential for tracking the virus and informing policy decisions. **The integration of health data with socioeconomic indicators provided a holistic view of the crisis.**

Spain's increasing reliance on scientific evidence, expert recommendations, and real-time monitoring guided and allowed for timely adjustments to its public health strategies and vaccination campaign, while transparent data sharing helped facilitate global collaboration.

The experience showed that reliable, timely, and accessible data is critical for informed decision-making and public trust. The Ministry of Health's Digital Health Strategy, introduced in 2021, laid the groundwork for advancing data interoperability, empowering patients, and integrating digital tools into healthcare processes. Efforts to enhance data integration, transparency, and real-time sharing across all levels of governance will be vital in improving crisis response capabilities.

Leveraging European collaboration

International collaboration efforts were a critical aspect of Spain's response to the COVID-19 pandemic. Spain actively participated in EU-wide initiatives, such as the European Union's Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF), which allocated approximately 2.5% of its €69.5 billion package to health-related investments. Such investments target the modernization and resilience of the health system, emphasizing high-tech equipment upgrades, digital transformation, and enhanced crisis preparedness. Collaboration with the pharmaceutical industry further supports innovative research and the production of essential medical supplies.

As part of broader European collaboration, Spain's participation in joint vaccine procurement and distribution was instrumental in achieving high immunization rates, showcasing the benefits of international partnerships. These efforts position Spain to address future health crises in an effective and coordinated way.

2.5.5 Main highlights from interview with senior policymakers

Unlike the other target countries included in this report, interviews with senior policymakers in Spain have not yet been conducted. As the PAIR project moves forward, efforts will focus on engaging key decision-makers in Spain to gather more comprehensive insights and perspectives.

3 Cross-country summary and analysis

Building on the detailed country-specific analyses provided in Chapter 2, this chapter presents a comprehensive cross-country summary and analysis of the COVID-19 pandemic preparedness and response strategies implemented by the five target countries, offering a comparative perspective that highlights shared challenges, successful strategies, and key lessons learned. The analysis focuses on identifying common themes, disparities, and opportunities for improvement, which can inform future pandemic preparedness and response efforts at both national and European levels.

This cross-country analysis is essential for understanding the broader implications of the pandemic and for developing robust, evidence-based recommendations for EU policymakers. By learning from the experiences of these countries, Europe can enhance its collective preparedness and resilience, ensuring that it is better equipped to manage future health crises.

3.1 Summary of key measures and strategies in target countries

The following table encapsulates the key initiatives, strategies, and policies undertaken by the five target countries in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. Each country adopted specific measures tailored to their administrative structure and healthcare system capabilities, which shaped their respective outcomes in terms of health, economic, and social impacts.

Table 1. Overview of key measures and strategies in PAIR's pilot countries

	Lockdown measures	Public health strategies	Economic support
Denmark	Early, less strict, public transport open, quick lifting	High testing, decentralized healthcare, effective vaccination	Wage compensation, business costs coverage, various financial supports
France	Strict, then localized, with night curfews and flexible measures	Masks mandates, tests, "White Plan", telemedicine	Unemployment allowance, state-guaranteed loans, €100B recovery plan
Latvia	Multiple states of emergency, strict travel restrictions	Centralized response, testing, contact tracing, increased health budgets	Downtime compensation, wage subsidies, tax reliefs, pro-investment initiatives

Italy	One of the strictest initially, then regional tiered restrictions	ICU increase, national mask mandates, vaccination campaign	'Cura Italia' and 'Rilancio' decrees, employment protection, digital investments
Spain	Two states of alarm, phased de-escalation	Case detection, surveillance, nationwide vaccination	Minimum living income, business support for at-risk employment sectors

3.2 Summary of outcomes and impact in target countries

The COVID-19 pandemic has had profound and multifaceted impacts, affecting health systems, economies, and social structures. Table 2 presents a summarized overview of these impacts in the PAIR's target countries. The health impact was characterized by varying mortality rates, hospital capacities, and vaccination rollouts. Economically, countries experienced different levels of recession, recovery, and government interventions. Socially, the pandemic exacerbated inequalities, mental health issues, and educational disparities. This table highlights the key outcomes and impacts in each of these dimensions.

Table 2. Overview of outcomes and impacts in PAIR's pilot countries

	Health impact	Economic impact	Social impact
Denmark	Low excess mortality, effective hospital management, high vaccination rates	Quick economic recovery, digital tools for resilience.	High public trust, compliance, digital tools for testing and vaccination
France	High initial prevalence, strain on hospitals, improved later management	Severe recession, economic support measures, social security deficit	Increased anxiety, depressive disorders, educational inequalities
Latvia	Moderate death rate, improved healthcare infrastructure, public health investment	GDP contraction, resilience, recovery, increased consumer spending and public investment.	Deepened social inequalities, digital infrastructure emphasis
Italy	High early mortality, strained regional healthcare, uneven resource distribution	Economic contraction, fallout in tourism and hospitality, government interventions	Daily life disruptions, exacerbated inequalities, mental health issues, social isolation

Spain	High mortality, strained urban healthcare, successful vaccination campaign	Severe economic impact, recession, job losses, economic instability	Mental health issues, vulnerable populations disproportionately affected, social and economic fallout.
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3.3 Shortcomings and challenges

3.3.1 Summary of shortcomings and challenges in target countries

Table 3. Overview of shortcomings and challenges in PAIR’s pilot countries

	Preparedness and initial response	Governance and decision-making	Public communication and trust	Healthcare coordination and capacity
Denmark	Initial underestimation, delayed response political-expert discrepancy	n/a	Mink scandal, crisis communication gaps	n/a
France	Degraded preparedness, PPE shortages, slow response	Centralized decision-making, overlooked local specifics	Inconsistent communication, weakened trust	Weak healthcare coordination, focus on hospitals
Latvia	Absence of National Civil Protection Plan and disaster management protocols	Fragmented decision-making, no centralized framework	Fluctuating public trust, misinformation	pre-existing healthcare limitations, staffing struggles
Italy	Outdated pandemic plans, insufficient protective gear, underdeveloped testing	Decentralized health system, uneven responses and resource allocation	Misinformation, lack of clear communication, public mistrust	Overwhelmed hospitals, regional disparities in healthcare capacity
Spain	Insufficient emergency stockpiles, hindered containment efforts	Conflicts among regional and central authorities, impaired national response	Challenges with public messaging, mixed understanding of guidelines	Initial shortages in ICU and medical supplies, regional disparities in healthcare access

3.3.2 Analysis of the main vulnerabilities, shortcomings and challenges in EU countries' COVID-19 pandemic preparedness and response

The COVID-19 pandemic presented an unprecedented challenge to public health systems worldwide. In the EU, despite existing frameworks and coordinated mechanisms, the response to the pandemic varied significantly across member states. This variability has exposed a range of vulnerabilities and shortcomings in pandemic preparedness and response strategies, which are outlined below.

- **Underfunded and inadequate preparedness:** the pandemic exposed that national pandemic preparedness in many countries was underfunded prior to the COVID-19 pandemic. One of the most significant challenges was the overwhelm of healthcare systems. There were underlying structural weaknesses in health systems including underdeveloped plans for procurement of supplies, shortages in healthcare personnel, as well as vulnerabilities in long-term care systems, leading to burnout and reduced capacity to handle the surge in patients. This lack of foresight hindered the initial response efforts and led to rapid depletion of critical resources during the early stages of the pandemic, which resulted in the need for crisis standards of care, prioritizing care to save the most lives possible due to limited resources.
- **Supply chain disruptions:** the COVID-19 pandemic introduced additional pressures on medical and medical device supply chains, leading to unprecedented spikes in demand and severe shortages, particularly of personal protective equipment and essential medicines, impacting the protection of healthcare workers and the treatment of patients.
- **Decentralised and centralised responses:** countries with decentralized health systems experienced inconsistencies in regional responses, contributing to disparities in case numbers and mortality rates across regions. This highlighted the need for better coordination and standardization of response measures. On the other hand, the absence of a unified national strategy in some countries led to fragmented responses, delaying crucial decisions like lockdowns and border closures. This resulted in heterogeneous impacts across regions, affecting the overall effectiveness of responses at national and EU levels.
- **Deficiencies in public communication and misinformation:** effective communication was undermined by the spread of misinformation and disinformation, while the lack of transparencies weakened public trust and hindered compliance with key

measures and response strategies. Many countries also struggled to implement timely containment strategies, which were crucial in the early stages of the pandemic.

- **Fragmented digital infrastructure:** the fragmented digital infrastructure across EU health systems led to fragmented health data, which in turn hindered the ability to share important healthcare information and impeded coordinated responses at both the national and EU levels.

By learning from these shortcomings and vulnerabilities, EU nations can enhance their resilience against future pandemics. Addressing them through targeted reforms and investments in healthcare infrastructure, testing, surveillance, and public communication is vital.

3.4 Good practices and lessons learned

3.4.1 Summary of good practices and lessons learned in target countries

Figure 1: Overview of good practices and lessons learned in PAIR's pilot countries

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3.4.2 Analysis: opportunities for future pandemic preparedness and response, key needs and expectations

The COVID-19 pandemic has brought to light numerous good practices and opportunities that can enhance future pandemic preparedness. By seizing these opportunities, EU countries can build more resilient health systems capable of responding more effectively to future global health challenges.

- **Adoption and scaling of digital health technologies**
 - the pandemic **accelerated the adoption** of digital health services such as teleconsultations and telemedicine, which have contributed to reduce the healthcare system's burden, increase access to care, and improve care coordination. Countries like Estonia and Denmark have been leaders in digital health, providing valuable lessons on integrating these technologies into everyday healthcare practices.
 - the pandemic exposed the need for robust health data infrastructure, **prompting new investments and legislative actions** to improve data governance across countries.
 - building on the success of digital health initiatives during the pandemic, opportunities include **enhancing the digital literacy** of populations and **improving the interoperability** of health data systems.
- **Leveraging the power of data**
 - many countries made significant improvements in **data availability to facilitate research**. For instance, Ireland developed the COVID-19 Data-hub and introduced the COVID-19 Biobank, standardizing data collection and making it available for research.
 - there was an **increase in international cooperation and data sharing**. European countries submitted data systematically to the ECDC and participated in the European Health Data Space.
- **Strong research and development ecosystem**

- the unprecedented speed of vaccine development underscores the potential for future collaborative research and rapid response to emerging health threats. Investing in a robust R&D ecosystem, including **partnerships between public entities and private companies**, can enhance preparedness and capacity to address future pandemics.
- effective collaborations between governments, private companies, and academia were essential in various aspects of the pandemic response. To capitalize on the benefits of public-private partnerships, there is an opportunity to **formalize frameworks** that facilitate them during non-crisis times, ensuring a more coordinated and rapid activation when crises arise.
- the need for rapid research development also pushed towards **decentralized clinical trials** across national boundaries and required comprehensive legislative actions to enable efficient use and sharing of health data.

These practices not only addressed the immediate challenges of the pandemic but also set a foundation for opportunities for improved response to future health crises through better preparedness, data-sharing mechanisms, and digital health. This underscores the necessity of continuous investment in health systems, the importance of agile policy frameworks, and the potential of innovative health technologies to transform healthcare delivery and emergency response

4 Europe's response to the COVID-19 pandemic

The previous section focused on analysing the pandemic responses of five individual countries and providing a comparative cross-country summary. This section shifts to examine Europe's collective response to the COVID-19 pandemic, exploring the policies, strategies, and mechanisms adopted by the European Union to address the crisis at a regional level.

The pandemic posed an unprecedented challenge globally, placing immense strain on public health systems, economies, and societies. In its initial stages, governments responded with a surge of nationalism, closing borders and competing for resources such as personal protective equipment, which revealed a lack of global solidarity. In Europe, these pressures exposed socio-economic inequalities and placed a disproportionate burden on the most vulnerable populations.

The crisis underscored the limitations of fragmented, unilateral approaches among EU Member States, highlighting the need for coordinated public health measures. Challenges such as supply chain disruptions, vaccine hesitancy, and inequitable access to resources reinforced the importance of treating health as a global public good. This prompted critical discussions about the EU's role in public health, ultimately leading to the establishment of the European Health Union.

At the same time, the pandemic provided the EU with an opportunity to strengthen its global health leadership and reshape its internal policies. The crisis underscored the necessity of collective action to build resilience and prepare for future emergencies. This section examines how the pandemic reshaped Europe's health strategies, demonstrating the importance of regional cooperation in addressing shared challenges.

4.1 EU Public health response to COVID-19

4.1.1 The European Health Union

The European Health Union (EHU) is a legislative initiative aimed at enhancing the EU's ability to coordinate responses to the COVID-19 pandemic and strengthening resilience and preparedness for current and future cross-border health threats. Launched on 11 November 2020 through the European Commission's Communication titled "*Building a European Health Union: Reinforcing the EU's resilience for cross-border health threats*," the EHU set out its foundational framework. The EHU envisions a collaborative approach among EU Member States to tackle health crises. It emphasizes the availability and affordability of medical supplies, fosters innovation, and promotes joint efforts to improve prevention, treatment, and aftercare for diseases. The key initiatives for the EHU were presented and

developed in three consecutive sets of actions from November 2020 to November 2022.

Overall, the EHU revolves around the following seven key initiatives:

A revised legal framework for serious cross-border health threats: On 11 November 2020, the EC put forward a proposal for a regulation on serious cross-border threats to health. In the light of lessons learned from the coronavirus crisis, it aimed to strengthen the EU's health security by revising Decision 1082/2013/EU (the 'Cross-Border Health Threats Decision'). The regulation introduces a Union-level prevention, preparedness, and response plan to complement national plans and provides mechanisms for recognizing public health emergencies at the EU level, guided by recommendations from the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC), World Health Organization (WHO), or an independent advisory committee.

Key features include a system for rapid alerts and coordinated responses to health threats, enhanced surveillance with case definitions, and networks for reference laboratories and monitoring disease outbreaks related to substances of human origin. Established by Directorate-General (DG SANTE), the Health Security Committee is tasked with coordinating national responses and communication during crises, while increased information sharing, international cooperation, and a joint procurement mechanism for medical countermeasures bolster EU-level actions.

The establishment of HERA: The European Health Emergency Preparedness and Response Authority (HERA), established on 16 September 2021 as a Directorate-General of the EC, marks a significant milestone in the development of the EHU. HERA is responsible for advancing the Commission's policies on health preparedness, crisis response, and strengthening the resilience of healthcare systems across Europe.

Its mission is to establish a robust and sustainable health security framework, addressing weaknesses highlighted during the COVID-19 pandemic, such as fragmented intelligence systems and global supply chain vulnerabilities. HERA operates in two key modes: preparedness and emergency response. In the preparedness phase, it collaborates with Member States to identify potential threats, support research, and enhance production capabilities. During emergencies, HERA acts under the direction of a Health Crisis Board, enabling rapid decision-making and action, including leveraging EU FAB—a European initiative to maintain flexible, multi-technology manufacturing capacity for vaccines and critical medical countermeasures.

With a €30 billion budget drawn from various EU financial instruments and potential contributions from private stakeholders and Member States, HERA is a cornerstone of the EU's efforts to strengthen its capacity to manage cross-border health threats effectively.

Revised mandates of the ECDC and EMA: In 2022, additional initiatives to consolidate the EHU included the expanded mandates of the ECDC and the European Medicines Agency (EMA). These changes addressed gaps revealed during the COVID-19 pandemic, such as incomplete data and communication challenges that had limited the ECDC's effectiveness. The revised mandate enhances the ECDC's capacity in preparedness, surveillance, risk

assessment, and early warning systems, while adopting a "One Health" approach that integrates human, animal, and environmental health (see section 4.3 below).

Similarly, the EMA's role was reinforced to better manage medical supply challenges. Lessons from the pandemic, including shortages of ventilators, surgical masks, and test kits, underscored the need for stronger mechanisms to monitor and address shortages of critical medicines and devices during emergencies. The EMA now oversees supply monitoring, coordinates clinical trials, provides scientific advice, and evaluates the safety and effectiveness of vaccines and treatments, contributing to a more unified and effective EU response to future health crises.

The European Health Data Space: A cornerstone of the EHU and a key milestone in the EU's digital transformation. Its primary goal is to enhance healthcare delivery across the EU by enabling individuals to have control over their health data, whether in their home country or other Member States. It also establishes a secure, trustworthy, and efficient framework for accessing health data, allowing researchers, innovators, public institutions, and industry to use this data under strict conditions to develop life-saving treatments, vaccines, and medical devices. Additionally, it promotes a unified market for digital health services and products.

This initiative is grounded in stringent standards for data privacy, interoperability, and security, including robust cybersecurity measures, which are essential for earning citizen trust and ensuring the project's resilience.

Pharmaceutical Strategy for Europe: Adopted on 25 November 2020, the Pharmaceutical Strategy for Europe aims to establish a future-proof regulatory framework while supporting the pharmaceutical industry in promoting research and technologies that address patients' therapeutic needs and resolve market inefficiencies. The strategy also acknowledges the weaknesses highlighted by the COVID-19 pandemic and includes measures to strengthen the resilience of the healthcare system.

It focuses on several key objectives, including ensuring access to affordable medicines for patients and addressing unmet medical needs, particularly in areas such as antimicrobial resistance and rare diseases. It also seeks to enhance the competitiveness, innovation, and sustainability of the EU pharmaceutical industry, encouraging the development of high-quality, safe, effective, and environmentally friendly medicines. In addition, the strategy aims to improve crisis preparedness and response mechanisms by diversifying and securing supply chains while addressing medicine shortages. Lastly, it emphasizes establishing a strong EU presence globally by upholding high standards of quality, efficacy, and safety in medicines.

Europe's Beating Cancer Plan: Presented in February 2021, it is a key initiative of the EHU, designed to enhance the EU's capacity in cancer prevention, treatment, and care. The plan addresses the structural challenges in cancer care, including the negative impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic, and is built around four key pillars: prevention, early detection, diagnosis and treatment, and improving the quality of life for cancer patients and survivors.

The plan integrates EU-wide policies in digitalization, research, innovation, and disease prevention, adopting a multisectoral "[Health in All Policies](#)" (HiAP) approach based on lessons learned from the pandemic, such as the benefits of resource pooling, goal setting, and Union-level coordination. It leverages €4 billion from the EU4Health programme and other EU instruments to enhance Member States' healthcare systems, promoting a comprehensive and sustainable cancer pathway.

EU global health strategy: In November 2022, the EC adopted the EU Global Health Strategy, building on lessons from the COVID-19 pandemic to enhance global health security, improve health outcomes, and tackle inequalities and emerging threats. As the external dimension of the EHU, the strategy emphasizes sustainable partnerships, strengthens preparedness and response mechanisms, and promotes equitable access to healthcare and resources.

The strategy focuses on improving health across all stages of life, advancing universal health coverage, and combating health threats, including pandemics, through a One Health approach. It addresses root causes of ill health such as poverty, inequality, climate change, and environmental degradation while leveraging digitalization, research, and a skilled workforce to drive progress.

Supporting stronger global health governance, the strategy advocates for a more accountable and effective WHO, deeper international cooperation, and expanded EU partnerships. The strategy also incorporates a HiAP framework to ensure diverse policies contribute meaningfully to health objectives. By addressing key drivers of poor health—climate change, food insecurity, conflict, and humanitarian crises—it strengthens prevention, preparedness, early detection, and response capacities, aiming to protect citizens from emerging health threats. This comprehensive framework, guiding EU health policies up to 2030 and aligning them to the [UN Sustainable Goals \(SDGs\)](#), reflects the EU's commitment to fostering a healthier, more equitable world.

4.1.2 EU vaccines and procurement strategies

Joint Procurement Agreement for medical countermeasures: Established in 2014, the Joint Procurement Agreement (JPA) is a voluntary EU initiative designed to enable Member States, EU institutions, and third countries to collectively acquire medical countermeasures for serious cross-border health threats. Rather than directly using EU funds for purchases, the JPA facilitates access to finalized contracts, allowing participating states to procure the necessary supplies using their national budgets. During the COVID-19 pandemic, the JPA emerged as a key instrument for coordinating pan-European procurement of PPE, ventilators, and devices essential for coronavirus testing. The first COVID-19-related joint procurement calls were launched in March 2020, followed by numerous additional procurement competitions for PPE, ventilators, and intensive care unit medicines. Successful tenders included contracts for gloves and coveralls worth €1.4 billion, eye and respiratory protection equipment for €150 million, and ventilators for €750 million.

Civil Protection and RescEU reserve: The European Civil Protection Mechanism (UCPM), established in 2001, plays a crucial role in coordinating disaster prevention, preparedness, and response efforts among EU Member States and other participating countries. Managed by the European Commission's DG ECHO, it provides comprehensive support for civil protection activities, including search and rescue operations, deployment of medical equipment, and repatriation of citizens.

RescEU, a strategic reserve established in 2019, is fully integrated into the UCPM. Operating as a last-resort safety net, RescEU complements the local and national capacities of participating states, offering critical resources independent of mechanisms like joint procurement under the JPA (see above).

The COVID-19 pandemic underscored the need for stronger, more coordinated systems, leading to significant enhancements in the UCPM's capabilities. Legislative amendments adopted in 2021 bolstered the mechanism's ability to respond quickly and effectively to large-scale emergencies. These reforms created a more flexible, cross-sectoral system to provide comprehensive support to Member States and their citizens. For 2021–2027, the UCPM was allocated a total budget of €3.319 billion, with €2.056 billion from the EU recovery instrument and €1.263 billion from the multiannual financial framework.

During the pandemic, RescEU played a pivotal role by coordinating and co-financing the delivery of PPE, medical equipment, repatriation flights, and medical team transport to affected countries.

EU vaccines strategy: The EU's collective public procurement strategy for COVID-19 vaccines diverged from the JPA model, instead utilizing Advance Purchase Agreements (APAs). Negotiated by the European Commission's DG SANTE with a joint team from seven Member States, the APAs ensured a united EU approach, promoting efficiency, equality, and solidarity. These agreements allowed the EU to pre-purchase or reserve vaccines, mitigating investment risks for manufacturers through upfront payments totalling €2.7 billion under the Emergency Support Instrument (ESI) Regulation framework. APAs also outlined an equitable vaccine distribution plan based on population size. By the end of 2020, agreements were finalized with six vaccine producers, with additional deals for Novavax and Valneva concluded in 2021. This enabled more than 2 000 operations to transport medical equipment, as well as approximately 515 health workers and 135 patients.

4.2 Budgetary commitment to health

The COVID-19 pandemic presented a significant challenge to the economies of the European Union, leading to an unprecedented recession. The EU responded to this extraordinary economic disruption with a comprehensive and decisive strategy, mobilizing all available resources. This period has marked a significant turning point for the EU, driving progress in economic integration.

The scale and impact of the pandemic underscored the need for innovative solutions and greater cooperation across the EU. The crisis coincided with ongoing discussions about the

future of the Economic and Monetary Union and the next multiannual financial framework, providing an opportunity to advance economic and fiscal integration.

The pandemic has reshaped the EU's approach to economic and fiscal governance. It compelled the Union to take unprecedented actions, breaking through long-standing economic and political barriers and fostering greater solidarity and risk-sharing among Member States. These initiatives signify a shift in fiscal policy and public investment priorities, emphasizing their central role in the EU's policy framework. Additionally, the crisis led to a reevaluation of fiscal oversight mechanisms and the potential for enhanced fiscal solidarity.

Emergency Support Instrument (ESI): ESI is a flexible, needs-based tool designed to address evolving demands as the EU transitions from the immediate pandemic response to recovery and prevention. Centrally managed by the European Commission and rooted in solidarity, the ESI complements other EU initiatives such as the JPA, rescEU, CRII, and national efforts. Activated in April 2020 with a €2.7 billion budget, the ESI provided financial support until January 2022 for securing COVID-19 vaccines, therapeutics, and the transport of medical teams and equipment. A significant portion of its budget was allocated to advance purchase agreements (APAs) under the EU vaccine strategy, while €220 million supported transport through its "mobility package." The ESI also facilitated the procurement of PPE, medical equipment, medicines, and active pharmaceutical ingredients, ensuring critical resources during the pandemic.

Coronavirus Response Investment Initiative (CRII): CRII, launched by the European Commission in March 2020, provided emergency support to EU Member States to address the COVID-19 crisis. It offered €8 billion in immediate liquidity to accelerate up to €37 billion in public investment, introduced flexibility in EU spending rules, and enabled access to the EU Solidarity Fund. Its follow-up initiative, CRII+, ensured a sustained response to the pandemic.

Delivered through the REACT-EU package, part of NextGenerationEU, the CRII extended crisis-response measures and supported green, digital, and resilient recovery projects. With a €50.6 billion budget, REACT-EU bridged the gap between emergency measures and long-term recovery plans, utilizing unspent EU cohesion policy funds to prioritize coronavirus-related health expenses, SME working capital, and short-term employment schemes. CRII+ further expanded support by allowing flexibility in structural fund use, offering 100% EU co-financing for cohesion programs, aiding vulnerable populations through food and material assistance, and supporting critical sectors like agriculture and fisheries. Together, CRII and CRII+ provided essential financial assistance with minimal administrative burden, targeting areas of greatest need.

NextGenerationEU: On May 2020, in response to the unprecedented crisis caused by the coronavirus pandemic, the European Commission proposed the temporary recovery

instrument NextGenerationEU, along with targeted reinforcements to the long-term EU budget for 2021–2027. Less than two months later, EU heads of state or government reached a political agreement on the package, with final adoption by the Council on 17 December 2020.

NextGenerationEU, a recovery instrument exceeding €800 billion, aims to tackle the economic and social impacts of the pandemic while building a greener, more digital, and resilient Europe. As the largest stimulus package ever funded by the EU, it supports reforms and investments aligned with the Union's strategic priorities and focuses primarily on four priorities:

1. **Ecological transition:** achieving climate neutrality and implementing measures to combat climate change.
2. **Digital transition:** expanding access to reliable internet connectivity, including 5G where possible, and investing in digital literacy for citizens.
3. **Macroeconomic stability:** investing in youth by creating opportunities for employment and education.
4. **Equity:** promoting actions and measures to combat all forms of hate and fostering initiatives for gender equality and tolerance towards the LGBTQI+ community.

At its centre is the [Recovery and Resilience Facility](#), which provides grants and loans to support Member States' recovery plans.

It also channels contributions to other critical programmes, including [REACT-EU](#), the [Just Transition Fund](#), [InvestEU](#), [Horizon Europe](#), and [RescEU](#). These aim to restore employment, strengthen healthcare systems, and foster economic growth and cohesion across the EU.

NextGenerationEU further supports businesses, particularly small and medium-sized enterprises, ensuring their resilience and financial stability. Strengthening strategic autonomy in essential supply chains is a critical focus, with investments targeting the Union's capacity in vital sectors. To prepare for future crises, the initiative funds efforts to bolster healthcare systems, stockpile medical supplies, and develop infrastructure for maintaining adequate levels of essential goods. By supporting the transition to a climate-neutral economy alongside economic recovery, NextGenerationEU ensures that Europe emerges stronger, more sustainable, and better equipped to face future challenges.

EU4Health programme: established in 2021, it aims to strengthen the EHU and address long-term health challenges by building more resilient, accessible, and robust healthcare systems. It follows earlier EU health programmes dating back to 2003. Initially, the health programme was set to lose its dedicated funding after 2020 and merge with the European Social Fund. However, the COVID-19 pandemic highlighted the critical need for common EU crisis preparedness, emphasizing the importance of cross-border health threat management.

With a budget of €5.3 billion for 2021–2027, EU4Health marks a significant increase in funding compared to previous programmes. As an independent funding initiative, it focuses on key health priorities, including improving health outcomes, protecting citizens, ensuring

access to essential medicines and crisis-relevant products, and strengthening health systems. The programme also supports the EU's resilience to cross-border health threats, Europe's Beating Cancer Plan, and the pharmaceutical strategy for Europe.

Embracing the "One Health" approach, EU4Health supports the digitalization of health systems, focuses on reducing antimicrobial resistance, and aims to enhance vaccination rates.

4.3 One Health approach

One Health, as defined by the [One Health High Level Expert Panel](#), is an integrated and unifying approach aimed at sustainably balancing and optimizing the health of people, animals, and ecosystems. It employs a risk-based framework to manage interactions among humans, livestock, wildlife, and the environment. By identifying critical control points and implementing risk-appropriate measures, One Health seeks to prevent spillovers of diseases between species and mitigate their consequences.

The COVID-19 pandemic underscored the necessity of unified strategies to address health threats, highlighting the importance of resilient and sustainable health systems. It emphasized the need for robust structures to prevent and mitigate risks at the human–animal–plant–environment interface while supporting sustainable development. This holistic approach tackles the root causes of zoonotic disease emergence and related health risks, fostering better prevention, preparedness, and science-based solutions to promote long-term health for all.

One Health also facilitates the identification and mitigation of future pandemic risks, informing sustainable public health policies. It promotes collaboration across sectors and disciplines, including public health, veterinary medicine, agriculture, environmental science, and policymaking, to ensure a coordinated and effective response to health challenges.

At the EU level, several existing policies align with the One Health principles, such as the [General Union Environment Action Programme to 2030](#) (8th EAP), the [Zero Pollution Action Plan](#), the [Animal Health Law](#), and the [Strategy on Climate Change](#). However, integrating One Health principles further into food and agriculture policies is crucial to achieving sustainable ecological, social, and economic systems.

Despite the lessons learned from health crises and disease outbreaks, investments in prevention, surveillance, and response systems under the One Health framework remain fragmented and insufficient. The persistent separation of sectors and disciplines continues to challenge the development and implementation of a truly integrated approach.

In November 2024, the European Commission received the [Scientific Advice Mechanism \(SAM\) report](#) on One Health governance in the EU. This non-binding report provides policy recommendations to strengthen One Health management, including fostering cross-disciplinary collaboration, expanding education and training, and promoting research and

innovation. These steps are vital for advancing integrated solutions to complex health challenges and ensuring a sustainable future.

4.4 WHO pandemic treaty

The WHO pandemic treaty is a proposed legally binding international agreement designed to strengthen pandemic prevention, preparedness, and response. It aims to address the gaps in global health governance highlighted during the COVID-19 pandemic, particularly the inequitable access to essential medical countermeasures and the inefficiencies in current international health frameworks. On behalf of the EU, the Council authorized the start of negotiations in March 2022, granting the EC a negotiation mandate.

A first draft of the treaty was released on November 2022, outlining principles informed by lessons from the COVID-19 pandemic and other global health crises. The draft emphasizes **the need for stronger preparedness systems** to ensure communities, governments, and all sectors are better equipped to handle future pandemics. The treaty proposes to address critical shortcomings in international responses to health crises, such as **the limitations of existing health and intellectual property laws** in providing timely and equitable access to vaccines, medicines, and diagnostics for the world's most vulnerable populations.

The treaty's focus areas include early detection and prevention of pandemics, building resilience for future crises, ensuring universal and equitable access to medical solutions, and strengthening the international health framework, with the WHO as the central coordinating authority. A "One Health" approach is also a core component, recognizing the interconnectedness of human, animal, and environmental health.

The proposed treaty also calls for sustained, predictable funding for health emergency preparedness, with contributions from domestic budgets to support preventive measures and ensure a robust global response to emerging health threats. Additionally, it proposes governance and oversight mechanisms to enhance transparency, accountability, and trust in international health efforts.

While the treaty was initially expected to be finalized in 2024, negotiations are still ongoing.

5 Recommendations for EU policymakers and integration of PAIR technologies

The COVID-19 pandemic has demonstrated the need for a shift from a reactive model of outbreak control to a **proactive, preventive approach**. Investments in One Health systems for prevention and control of zoonotic diseases and early action limits the rising costs of control and prevents broader impact globally.

In this sense, **PANPOC**'s rapid detection of respiratory RNA viruses with pandemic potential in human, animal, and environmental samples, and **PANRISK**'s predictive analysis can both support ongoing preparedness efforts by enabling policymakers to anticipate and plan for emerging pandemic threats, thereby ensuring that resources are better allocated, and preparedness measures are continuously updated.

Below are five policy recommendations to improve future pandemic preparedness and response along with specific ways that PAIR technologies can be applied:

1. Enhance data integration, harmonization and utilization
2. Institutionalise comprehensive surveillance and prevention measures
3. Bolster international cooperation and coordination
4. Support supply chain resilience
5. Promote equitable, inclusive, and accessible health services

5.1 Enhance data integration, harmonization, and utilization

Data serves as the backbone of pandemic management by enabling timely decision-making and resource allocation. Although it is not known what form the next crisis will take, data will be fundamental to tackle it. Better use of data and the tools to convert it into actionable information for decision-making is critical to surveillance of new threats.

Since the COVID-19 outbreak, EU countries reported improved data reporting and enhanced the timeliness of data to inform policy choices and to foster more efficient resource use. These gains must be consolidated and built upon, together with investment in digital infrastructure, to improve the response to future crises.

Enhanced data integration and utilization ensure that all relevant health data, whether on infection rates, hospital availability, or vaccination statuses, is collected, harmonized, and accessible. This unified approach aids in early detection of outbreaks, efficacy assessment of public health measures, and tailoring of interventions to specific populations or regions.

Technologies like PANPOC and PANRISK can streamline this process by integrating diverse data streams and applying advanced analytics to interpret this data, providing actionable insights that can guide policy and pandemic response efforts.

PANPOC collects and gathers real-time health data from EU member states, ensuring data harmonization through standardized formats and common indicators. PANRISK utilizes this harmonized data to perform dynamic risk assessments, projecting potential outbreaks.

5.2 Institutionalise comprehensive surveillance and prevention measures

A stronger international surveillance system with continuous information gathering, risk assessment, and rapid coordination of responses would have facilitated a quicker response to the COVID-19 pandemic.

Surveillance systems help in the monitoring of disease spread and other health indicators, making it essential to establish these systems as a permanent fixture of public health infrastructure. Continuous surveillance enables health authorities to detect and respond to infectious disease threats early, potentially containing them before they escalate into more significant outbreaks.

By incorporating technologies like PANPOC for real-time data collection, and PANRISK for risk assessment, the surveillance system can become proactive rather than reactive, facilitating more pre-emptive measures to prevent widespread transmission.

In tandem, PAIR technologies can continuously monitor disease outbreaks across the EU. This system can detect potential threats, triggering early warning notifications to the appropriate agencies. The risk levels associated with detected threats would be assessed and preventive actions or interventions based on predictive modelling and historical data analysis would be recommended.

5.3 Bolster international cooperation and coordination

Pandemics are global challenges that do not respect national borders. International decision-making was challenged at the beginning of the pandemic and the speed of response was compromised. Effective international cooperation and coordination allows countries to share crucial information, including data on emerging pathogens, effective treatment protocols, and best practices for containment.

The unparalleled success and speed of COVID-19 vaccine development saved millions of lives. Massive public funding was provided for research, development and manufacturing capacity, although vaccine distribution was ultimately inequitable. Prioritising innovation and exploring new incentives would help prepare the global community for future pandemics.

This collaborative approach is vital for managing common threats and coordinating responses to ensure consistency and effectiveness across regions. Internationally coordinated approaches are required for technology transfer and management of intellectual property for essential health technologies.

PANPOC and PANRISK can facilitate and strengthen such cooperation by enhancing the collective ability to manage pandemic risks more efficiently. The technologies can assist in coordinating response efforts through the sharing of information, and by evaluating the effectiveness of different strategies utilized in various regions and recommending optimized approaches based on collective intelligence and risk assessments.

5.4 Support supply chain resilience

The pandemic highlighted the vulnerabilities in global supply chains, particularly for essential medical supplies and pharmaceuticals. The supply of medical products hampered the initial response to the COVID-19 pandemic, and almost all EU countries reported difficulties in obtaining personal protective equipment, as well as testing materials, and ventilators. Although later in the pandemic, international trade enabled a large increase in the availability of vaccines and essential medical devices, barriers to trade hampered distribution. For instance, difficulties in identifying countries involved in supply chains undermined the assessment of risk.

Strengthening supply chain resilience ensures that there is continuity in the supply of critical goods during a pandemic. International cooperation around stockpiling and distribution of scarce products would promote more equitable and effective responses. It is crucial for preventing shortages of medical supplies and equipment, which are pivotal for pandemic response and for maintaining routine health services delivery.

The data from PANPOC and PANRISK can support proactive management of resources during a crisis, leading to the early identification of bottlenecks and potential shortages.

5.5 Promote equitable, inclusive, and accessible health services

Vulnerable populations make for vulnerable health systems, and maximising people's health before a crisis minimises the damage to the population. Equity in health service availability and accessibility ensures that all segments of the population have the necessary protection against health crises, reducing overall community vulnerability. Special attention needs to be paid to marginalized and underserved communities who often suffer disproportionately due to systemic inequities. Promoting healthier lifestyles and addressing wider socioeconomic determinants of poor health, such as poverty and unemployment, is critical to mitigating the impact of future health crises.

A strong primary care system offering universal health coverage helps to improve health prior to a crisis. Additionally, including mental health considerations in crisis preparedness and response planning should be routine.

Portable tools like PANPOC ensure equitable and inclusive data collection that can represent all demographics across the EU.

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Conclusion

These recommendations aim to reduce the impact of future pandemics on EU health systems, societies, and economies. Policies should not only address current issues but also be **forward looking and anticipate** future challenges by ensuring physical resources, data, governance and financing mechanisms are in place.

Together, PANPOC and PANRISK technologies provide a comprehensive toolkit for enhancing pandemic preparedness by improving the speed and accuracy of pathogen identification and enriching the decision-making process with robust predictive insights.

6 Conclusions and next steps

The report, “*COVID-19 Preparedness and Response: Shortcomings and Opportunities – An Initial Analysis for EU Policymakers*” offers a preliminary evaluation of pandemic preparedness and response at both national and EU levels. It marks the outcome of the work conducted during the first year of the PAIR project, under WP10 - Task 10.5, “Integration and Deployment in Health Policies and Health and Care Systems.”

The analysis centres on the PAIR target countries—Denmark, France, Latvia, Italy, and Spain—which will serve as testing grounds for the project’s innovative tools, PANPOC and PANRISK. PANPOC, a diagnostic point-of-care instrument, aims to deliver cost-effective, portable testing, while PANRISK, an AI-driven prognostic platform, is designed to enhance early decision-making during health crises. These tools will be piloted to refine their functionality, validate their effectiveness, and provide evidence for their broader adoption in pandemic management frameworks. Employing a dual methodology of desk research and structured interviews with senior policymakers, the report evaluates preparedness and response strategies, identifying key measures, outcomes, challenges, and good practices. A cross-country comparison complements the country-specific analyses, revealing shared challenges, disparities, and lessons learned while offering insights into the structural and operational aspects of pandemic management.

At the European Union level, the report highlights significant gaps in cross-border coordination, resource allocation, and governance structures. However, it also documents substantial advancements, including the establishment of the European Health Union. The European Health Union aims to strengthen the EU’s health crisis management by promoting harmonized surveillance systems, equitable access to health resources, and effective communication strategies. The report acknowledges the role of collective EU initiatives, such as vaccine procurement mechanisms and financial frameworks, in mitigating early fragmentation among national responses.

Building on this foundation, subsequent phases of Task 10.5 will prioritize active engagement with policymakers at national, European, and international levels. Stakeholders will be systematically identified and mapped through desk research, expert consultations, and collaboration with PAIR’s partners to ensure comprehensive representation of relevant decision-makers and influencers. Engagement efforts will involve the preparation of concise briefing notes that aim to provide actionable insights, as well as formal briefings to present in-depth findings and tailored recommendations. These formal briefings will target key institutions, including the European Parliament, the European Commission, the Health Emergency Preparedness and Response Authority (HERA), the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC), and the World Health Organization (WHO), ensuring that findings are effectively translated into actionable policy guidance.

The ultimate goal is to equip policymakers with robust tools and evidence-based strategies to better prepare for and respond to future pandemics. By addressing specific gaps and deficiencies identified in both national and international evaluations, this work will contribute to fostering a more resilient, cohesive, and effective European health system capable of tackling future health emergencies.

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